

SATISFACTORY

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AREA	Augmented Reality for Enterprise Alliance
BS	Business Scenario
BSC	Business Scenarios
CMMS	Computerised Maintenance Management System
DoW	Description of Work
DV	Decision Variables
EC	European Commission
EIS	Executive Information System
ES	Evaluation Scenario
EU	European Union
HMI	Human Machine Interface
iDSS	Integrated Decision Support System
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
PCC	Principle Control Centers
PI	Performance Indicators
PIS	Performance Indicator Systems
PMS	Production Management Systems
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
UCD	User Centred Design

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020).

The goal of this deliverable is to report on the SatisFactory Evaluation Methodology and Plans that have been developed in the scope of Task T5.2 ("Evaluation Methodology and Plans"). The methodology and plans have been presented in the M14 version of the deliverable, i.e. D5.1.2. In the second iteration of the deliverable, i.e. D5.2.2, the evaluation scenarios and tests have been revised and updated where necessary, to keep in line with the developments of the SatisFactory components. Moreover, the timing of activities in the evaluation process has been updated, taking into consideration the actual course of implementations. It is noted that the methodology has been tested and validated at the industrial lab environment of CERTH/CPERI, so that it can be then used at the industrial pilots of COMAU and SUNLIGHT. Those results are being presented in D5.5 Final System Evaluation Report.

The goal of this deliverable is to prepare the evaluation methodology, plan and tools foreseen in the project, providing an evaluation framework for adequately assessing the level of fulfilment of the project objectives and the value of its results in terms of their appreciation by the factory workers and the decision makers. It is noted that Task 5.2 (and D5.2) are related with activities of T1.3 Use cases and Scenarios, T5.3 Deployment of Industry lab use case, T5.4 Industrial pilot demonstrators and T5.5 Evaluation, Results consolidation and Lessons learned. In order to achieve this goal specific evaluation scenarios and tests are defined that will enable reporting measurable results for the evaluation of the overall SatisFactory framework, covering all functionalities and identified business scenarios.

The evaluation framework is described, starting with the objectives which are presented along with the methodology and deriving criteria. After that, the Key Performance Indicators that will be used for the evaluation are given, following the structure of the defined criteria. It should be mentioned here that the overall approach serves three purposes: i) the evaluation of the performance of the components from the end users point of view, ii) the workers' satisfaction following the user-centred approach, iii) the overall SatisFactory framework performance. Moreover, a short description of the Pilot sites is provided, pointing out any legal and operational constraints that need to be considered in the process.

The specific evaluation tests to be performed in order to address the defined evaluation scenarios, along with the corresponding evaluation metrics which will be utilized per test for the extraction of measurable results as well as, the evaluation plan to be followed during pilot realization for tests execution, are described in Chapter 4. Additionally, the concept of the evaluation workshops and information session is presented, along with their time schedule for user experience evaluation. The dedicated questionnaires which have been prepared to are provided in the annexes.

The analysis of the results of the evaluation at CERTH/CPERI are given in Chapter 5 and the respective raw data are available in Annex V.

1. INTRODUCTION

The scope of the SatisFactory evaluation framework that has been set up is to allow the evaluation of the outcomes of the project, from the end users' point of view and experience. After all, the SatisFactory project concept puts the users in the centre of the development, the evaluation of performance and the acceptance.

Following the integration of the different components and toolkits and the installations at the industrial lab and the pilot sites, the SatisFactory framework performance is going to be evaluated along with its ability to offer a satisfying working environment. In order to do that, several tools have been developed for data collection and special focus is put on the evaluation of end users acceptance, addressing also the User Centred Design (UCD) methodological framework of the project.

The evaluation approach is based on a combination of indicators assessing Satisfaction, Business facilitation and Ease of use. Data are collected after the initial and final implementation at all shop floors from both the workers and the decision makers.

2. SATISFACTORY EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

2.1 OBJECTIVES OF THE EVALUATION

The objective of the SatisFactory evaluation framework is to provide the methodology to evaluate the fulfilment of the project objectives with respect to the user (workers and decision makers) requirements. Therefore, the scope of the evaluation process is to assess the fulfilment of the project objectives and the interoperation between the components of SatisFactory platform and the different stakeholders. In order to do that, the evaluation process requires the establishment of a series of evaluation scenarios and tests to be performed. The user-centred design approach is extended also here, using an iterative process, as it has been adopted throughout the project. Following the UCD concept, the evaluation is running in parallel with all design and integration activities and it involves the initial adaptation of the proposed framework into real-time conditions, its operation in the pilots, along with an extended period of evaluation.

It is noted that the definition of the framework for the evaluation of factory workers and decision makers' appreciation starts from the **project objectives**:

- 1 Context-aware control and re-adaptation of shop floor production facilities for increased productivity and flexibility in use of shop floor resources
- 2 Improvement of attractiveness and productivity through collaboration, social interaction and gamification approaches
- 3 Real-time knowledge-sharing and AR-based collaboration and training services
- 4 Improved shop floor feedback and decision making for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort
- 5 Adaptive and augmented interfaces for collaboration, knowledge sharing and real time support

As it has been discussed the solution has been deployed and evaluated in an Industrial Lab pilot and in large-scale Industrial Facilities from the Automotive and Energy factory domain (6th project objective).

However, it is necessary to determine a set of objectives, which are related to the end-user perspective, the **evaluation objectives**. The project objectives need to be translated into a set of end-user expectations and requirements that constitute the basis for the evaluation methodology. The fulfilment of these objectives will be evaluated through the various Business Scenarios (BSCs), which are defined in D1.2, which in turn has capitalised from D1.1. Moreover, the D2.1 has served as a basis for the components to be evaluated. The evaluation objectives identified are:

1. Performance improvement
2. Real-time knowledge-sharing
3. AR assisted operation and training
4. Collaborative working environment
5. Ease of use and overall satisfaction

Figure 1 Evaluation Objectives

Performance Improvement refers to the way end-users perform their jobs and the outcome of their work. SatisFactory will provide the ability to monitor the actions of the operator within the shop floor, verifying their correctness according to the knowledge base already acquired and, then, on the one hand, guiding the worker, on the other hand, reporting any deviation or irregularity in order to keep the optimum balance between worker satisfaction and performance. Thus, the evaluation of the latter aspect will make use of KPIs that aim to evaluate the outcome of the worker’s daily activities, taking into consideration the introduction of new technologies and tools, such as AR devices, sensors, cameras and so forth.

Real-time knowledge sharing includes many things in an operating environment. A worker requires a set of information, resources, data and guidelines, in order to successfully and timely complete a task. A supervisor or manager needs to have an overview of the available resources (equipment, personnel, time etc.), the priorities from the production department, the status of equipment and more, in order to organise the busy factory hive. To this end, the objective is to evaluate how SatisFactory facilitates knowledge sharing and timely response to the continuously changing conditions at the shop floor.

The factories of the future are going to be managed and operated by the managers and workers of the future. The term “collaboration” embraces many different aspects within an operating environment such as knowledge sharing, interaction, and gamification. A **Collaborative Working environment** is more attractive, facilitates social interaction, promotes the use of new technologies and improved industrial manufacturing methods, and

offers decision support for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort. In this context, we refer to the *Collaborative Working environment* in order to evaluate the novelty of the solutions proposed and, in particular, the level of appreciation of the innovative features which are introduced by SatisFactory.

AR assisted operation and training is one of the cutting-edge solutions presented within SatisFactory. In an operating mode, a certain Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) can be presented to the worker in an augmented reality environment, empowering him/her with the possibility to be more efficient, safer and to improve memorisation without interrupting the operation at the shop floor. The tools developed offer a real on-the-job training and assist operation in real-time. The training platform aims to leverage the intuitiveness of AR to deliver “on-the-job” training and education for both entry and senior-level workers.

Ease of use and overall satisfaction from the end users’ point of view, are necessary for the acceptance of new technologies and devices within the shop floor. Easy-to-use devices facilitate the workers to perceive the added value introduced by the adoption of such devices in relation with the level of knowledge and skills required to use them. Moreover, the importance of overall satisfaction in the workplace needs to be emphasised, so that the degree of fulfilment of every user expectation is taken into consideration.

The relation of the project objectives to the evaluation objective is clear and straightforward. It should be noted that for the evaluation of the project objectives, certain KPIs have been set out in the DoW for the 3 years of the project duration. The results for the first year have been analysed within D8.2.

For the measurement of the fulfilment of the evaluation objectives, a set of evaluation scenarios and test are presented in this deliverable, based on the methodology and criteria analysed in the next sections. It is noted that for the second iteration of the current deliverable the evaluation objectives have been examined and it was decided by the partners that they are still valid and in accordance with the implementation of the project.

2.2 EVALUATION METHODOLOGY AND CRITERIA

The evaluation methodology of the SatisFactory framework depicts the user-centric approach that is in the core of this project. The worker involvement and satisfaction need to be carefully evaluated and improved, because the adoption of new technologies and tools is often delayed or even hindered by the workers refusal to integrate them to their daily activities. Two main methodologies have been combined; the user-centric approach and the ECOGRAI method.

2.2.1 Human-centric Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation within SatisFactory follows the human-centered design approach according to the ISO 9241-210 Standard 210 (ISO 2010). This was introduced in SatisFactory Deliverable D1.1 - User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines and will be shortly summarized here as introduction to the evaluation methodology.

The main characteristic is the iterative approach, i.e. we apply a continuous circle of gaining domain knowledge, deriving requirements, producing design solutions and evaluating whether these solutions meet the requirements. This leads to new knowledge, which requests for creating new requirements or revising existing ones etc. The requirements are managed with the JIRA tool, which allows for creating a network of interrelated design artefacts in the interest of achieving design traceability as advocated by ISO 9241, see also (Ramesch and Jarke 2001).

2.2.1.1 Evaluation Approaches for First Iterations

During the first iterations, the used methods focus on evaluating whether the developed solutions are effective and efficient for completing the envisaged tasks. Besides assessing the solutions, in this period optimizing them is also possible, so the methodologies also try to result in suggestions for improving the former iterations. For this, we consider the following methods appropriate.

2.2.1.1.1 Focus Groups

A focus group is a group of end users or other experts for a system under examination. The focus group discusses given designs and can also revise the designs during the focus group session. However, the examined design must have been designed by somebody else. A moderator makes sure that the group stays on topic and that everyone contributes to the discussion.

Main purpose of a focus group session is to test a product idea. Mental models, personal preferences, reluctances and wishes shall be identified. In addition, focus groups can be used in order to validate user requirements.

The focus group shall be as homogeneous as possible. I.e. the boss should not participate in the same focus group as the secretary does. The ideal number of participants is 7.

2.2.1.1.2 Field Studies

The actual product is tested by potential end users. Depending on the state of the product, the field study can be conducted with a prototype in a lab environment or with a more mature product deployed in a productive environment.

The users perform typical test task with the product. The test person asks the users to think aloud, i.e. to verbalize every thought during task execution. The test person is foremost an observer and does not explain anything about the project but tries to find out how much the users can achieve with the product without explanation. However, the test person can ask the users questions if rationale or uncertainties in some of the users' actions cannot be observed. And, of course, quiet participants need gentle reminders to continue thinking aloud.

In this sense, for every critical situation of use, it is tested, whether this situation is a problem according to ISO 9241-110 (ISO 2006). Thinking aloud helps to identify reasons.

The results are documented during and after the session. If several user groups exist, testing with 5 users per group detect the majority of critical situations.

2.2.1.1.3 Expert Evaluations

Besides letting the evaluation be performed by users, there are also methods which can be performed by experts. This is especially useful if it is for some reason difficult to let users participate.

One expert evaluation is the inspection on basis of user requirements. For this, an expert tests whether the product does what it should do. The user requirements, which were developed in scope of the user context, are the test criteria. The overall system assessment is the sum of degrees of fulfilment of every user requirement. Target is the optimization of a system by extension of the possible effectively executable tasks.

During a scenario-based walkthrough, 2 experts execute typical tasks using the system. For every critical situation of use, it is tested, whether this situation is a problem according to ISO 9241-110 (ISO 2006). So, this approach is like a field study with the difference that it is conducted by experts instead of end users.

2.2.1.1.4 Heuristic Evaluation

Separated from each other, several usability experts evaluate a system by 10 heuristics. On average 5 experts are able to detect 75% of all usability issues. This is a cheap and effective method to detect the majority of issues, developed by (Nielsen 1994). It can also be conducted in an early stage of development. However, it cannot completely replace user tests as it will not identify all issues.

The heuristic evaluation is conducted in 4 phases. In the preparation phase, the experts familiarize themselves with the product. Then, the actual evaluation is conducted according to the heuristics by 3-5 experts, optimally 2 runs, and 1-2 hours each. Each identified issue is assessed and documented according to its severity on a 5-point scale, taking into account its frequency, impact and persistency. In the results phase, the experts sit together in order to group problems according to the ratings. In the final solution finding phase, the experts brainstorm together with the developers.

The 10 heuristics are:

1. The system should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.
2. The system should speak the user's language, with words, phrases and concepts familiar to the user, rather than system-oriented terms. Follow real-world conventions, making information appear in a natural and logical order.
3. Users often choose system functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.
4. Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing. Follow platform conventions.
5. Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.
6. Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the dialogue to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.
7. Accelerators—unseen by the novice user—may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the system can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.
8. Dialogues should not contain information which is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.
9. Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.
10. Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.

2.2.1.2 Final Evaluation Approaches

The evaluation of final implementations is checking for overall usability and user experience and whether the general ergonomic principles according to ISO 9241-110 are met (ISO 2006). Of course, at this point in time, solutions cannot be optimized anymore, so the methodologies are only focussing on assessing but not on optimizing. The main method for final evaluations is a field study with the deployed product (cf. Section 2.2.1.1.2).

Alternatively, the questionnaires introduced in this Section can be used. All questionnaires are listed in Annexe I.

2.2.1.2.1 SUS – System Usability Scale

The System Usability Scale (Brooke 1996) measures level of required help, level of required introduction and complexity of a system. It is a commonly used method for computing subjective usability assessment of participants to a single number. The SUS is very lightweight since only 10 questions need to be answered by participants.

(Sauro 2011) collected data from over 5000 users across over 500 system usability scale evaluations. He compiled them to a benchmark to which an own SUS value can be compared.

2.2.1.2.2 AttrakDiff

AttrakDiff captures the users' perception of a product. A free-to-use online tool is provided at <http://attrakdiff.de/>. Users are presented 28 pairs of opposite adjectives and are asked to assign these to the product under examination using a 7-point scale. Different adjective-pairs are then grouped and evaluated to the dimensions as follows (Hassenzahl 2003).

- **Pragmatic Quality (PQ):**
Indicates how successful users are in achieving their goals using the product.
- **Hedonic Quality - Stimulation (HQ-S):**
Mankind has an inherent need to develop and move forward. This dimension indicates to what extent the product can support those needs in terms of novel, interesting and stimulating functions, contents and interaction- and presentation-styles.
- **Hedonic Quality (HQ-I):**
Indicates to what extent the product allows users to identify with it.
- **Attractiveness (ATT):**
A global value that is based on the other dimensions. Hedonic and pragmatic qualities are independent of one another and contribute equally to the rating of attractiveness (Hassenzahl 2001).

2.2.1.2.3 User Experience Questionnaire

UEQ – the user experience questionnaire – is similar to AttrakDiff in the sense that users must assign a product on a 7-point scale to 26 pairs of opposite adjectives. Most of the UEQ adjectives are different to those used by AttrakDiff. UEQ calculates scores for the following categories (Rauschenberger 2013).

- **Attractiveness:**
General impression towards the product. Do users like or dislike the product? This scale is a pure valence dimension.
- **Efficiency:**
Is it possible to use the product fast and efficiently? Does the user interface look organized?
- **Perspiciuity:**
Is it easy to understand how to use the product? Is it easy to get familiar with the product?
- **Dependability:**
Does the user feel in control of the interaction? Is the interaction with the product confident and predictable?
- **Stimulation:**
Is it interesting and exciting to use the product? Does the user feel motivated to further use the product?
- **Novelty:**
Is the design of the product innovative and creative? Does the product grab users' attention?

2.2.2 ECOGRAI Evaluation Methodology

ECOGRAI is a method originally introduced to design and to implement Performance Indicator Systems (PIS) for industrial organizations and used by the decision makers of the Production Management Systems (PMS) to measure the achievement of their objectives (Doumeingts *et al.*, 1995).

The approach involves two stages:

- a) Top-down approach for the logical process of analysis, decomposing the objectives of the strategic levels into objectives for operational levels. For SatisFactory this is depicted in the selection on the areas that the management and supervisor levels wish to focus in terms of assessing the technologies and tools through the project.
- b) Bottom-up approach for the concrete process of participative implementation. Forming the conditions that allow to support the dialogue between the different company levels allows the identification of indicators that are acceptable by and make sense to the future users of the products.

The six steps of the ECOGRAI method are depicted below.

Figure 2 The six steps of the ECOGRAI method

Application of ECOGRAI to the SatisFactory project

The ECOGRAI methodology will be capitalised within SatisFactory for the selection of the KPIs to be investigated in order to evaluate the fulfilment of the project objectives and the value of its results at the workers' and at the decision makers' levels. A detailed analysis will be based on this methodology, taking also advantage of the existing evaluation framework and KPIs already existing in the shop floors. Certain phases are split into sub-phases for ease of the implementation (Lobna *et al.*, 2013).

2.2.2.1 Phase 0: Modelling of the Production System Control Structure and Identification of the PCC

Phase 0.1 Modelling of the Production System Control Structure

The shop floors involved in SatisFactory have an already defined structure of their production system. However, this structure should be revisited with a critical eye, in order to help define the decision centres, their activities, their links, as well as the objectives and the drivers. The structure can be depicted using the existing management tools and/or the GRAI Grid, distinguishing the strategic, tactical and operational levels. It should be also noted that the hierarchical and functional approaches are also considered.

Phase 0.2 Identification of the PCC

The PCC are, in fact, the decision centres, which have a principal influence on the system control as a consequence of their activities. They are traditionally available at the strategic level, but not necessarily at the tactical and operational levels. The end users will identify the set of PCC that covers the various functions (engineering, manufacturing, quality and maintenance) of all grids and at various decision levels.

In order to identify a PCC, the GRAI grid must be considered, in the form of a matrix with a horizontal production axis and a vertical managerial axis. On the managerial or control axis the various decision levels in the Production System are presented, usually as strategic, tactical and operational levels. This categorisation is kept here, taking into consideration the management, supervisor and worker levels. On the production axis the activities required to carry out the complete manufacturing procedure within the SatisFactory shop floors are included (such as design, manufacture, maintenance, quality, delivery, recycling).

A decision centre is defined by a function and decision level cross. From these decision centres the Principal Control Centres are selected and defined, as those having the most influence on the system control, because of the activities taking place within them.

2.2.2.2 Phase 1: Identification of the PCC Objectives and Coherence Analysis

Phase 1.1: Identification of the PCC Objectives

The objectives usually come from the Business Plan of the infrastructure. In the SatisFactory shop floors they are primarily based in terms of optimisation of the triplet Quality / Cost / Customer Satisfaction, with the Lead Time being incorporated into the Cost and Customer Satisfaction aspect. However, the triplet becomes a rectangular within this project, bringing up front the importance of Worker Satisfaction.

Phase 1.2 and 1.3: Identification of the Global and PCC Objectives for each function and Coherence Analysis

The global or overall objectives and the objectives of each function need to be aligned. The main issue at this step of the analysis is to make sure that the existing links between the global/overall objectives of the various functions are well identified in order to make sure that there are no perverse effects. In the case of such an effect, the objectives assigned to a function might prevent another function to achieve its objectives.

2.2.2.3 Phase 2: Identification of the PCC Drivers and analysis of the conflicts

The Drivers are the one of the most important parts of the procedure, which is usually overlooked. They must be defined, taking into account that they have intra-function and inter-function influences. For each PCC, the aim here is to evaluate the relationships with the Drivers, the degree, the origin of the influence and whether the Driver has a direct or indirect effect on the considered objective.

2.2.2.4 Phase 3: Identification of the PCC PIs and Internal Coherence Analysis

Phase 3.1: Identification of the PIs for the PCCs

At this step, the methodology moves on with the identification of Performance Indicators for each PCC. The approach uses the knowledge of all the people involved in the study and this identification is validated by an internal coherence analysis inside each Principal Control Centre. However, this detailed analysis can result to a great number of PIs, in order to cover all aspects of the performed tasks within a PCC. It is imperative to associate the PIs with the objectives and to select the few that will form the set of Key Performance Indicators, the KPIs.

Phase 3.2: Internal Coherence Analysis of the PCC

The Objectives, the Drivers and the Performance Indicators need to be consistent for each PCC. Cyclic diagrams or coherence panels can be built to allow for the identification of links between the elements of the PCC, as well as the weight of their contribution. The latter is complimenting the effort within Phase 3.1, in order to end up with a set of KPIs, rather than with an extensive list of PIs.

2.2.2.5 Phase 4: Design of the PI Information System

An indicator is a means to measure a certain activity. There are three aspects that need to be considered: a) which data is necessary and b) how will they be processed, in order to generate the values of the indicators, c) what are the target values or at least an acceptable operating level. Certain PIs exist already in the shop floors, but they mainly address the technical part of the implementation and the influence on the final product/service. Within T5.2, focus is also given into the evaluation of the overall solution, so, when necessary, the partners can use a specification sheet for each indicator which breaks down the PI and makes it more understandable and reusable.

Table 1 Specification Sheet for PI of the ECOGRAI method

ECOGRAI Study	Phase 4: Indicator Specification	Function: Decision Centre: Period:
<p><i>Indicator</i></p> <p><i>Objectives</i></p> <p><i>Drivers</i></p> <p><i>Basic Information</i></p> <p><i>Origin</i></p> <p><i>Processing</i></p> <p><i>Required evolution</i></p> <p><i>Possible perverse effects and possible influence on other indicators</i></p> <p><i>Actions to make the indicator evolve in the required direction</i></p> <p><i>Description and demonstration (e.g. representation using graphics)</i></p>		

It is noted that the Specification Sheet is an extensive tool that might not be fully capitalised within the duration of the SatisFactory project, as iterations and reworks show more complete results after consecutive implementations. It is much more easy to use PIs already defined and used by the end users. However, the basic aspects can be considered, in order to select the most representative KPIs.

2.2.2.6 Phase 5: Integration of the Performance Indicator information system in the Production information system

This phase is optional and it can be supported by the use of an EIS (Executive Information System) tool. In case of existing data bases it is an option that can be applied or it can be revisited once they will be in use. Moreover, existing information systems supporting specific functions or operations (such as the CMMS for the Maintenance operation) can be

considered. They are valuable not only for the generation of PIs in the previous phases of the analysis, but also in the integration phase, as they are part of the Production information system.

2.2.3 Combined Evaluation Methodology

The two methodologies described in the previous sections are complimentary, as they address the evaluation issue from different points of view, considering the human factor, as well as the system for the availability and sharing of information and influences within an industrial environment. The combined evaluation methodology allows for the usage of tools from both approaches that are suitable for each shop floor. The methodology is translated into the evaluation criteria described in the following section. It is worth mentioning that the evaluation methodology has been revisited and accepted by the project partners during the period that leads to the second iteration of the current deliverable.

Moreover, considering both methodologies, a set of Criteria and respective Evaluation Tests has been set out, taking into account the human-centred design approach, the principle control centres and decision variables definition, under the umbrella of the heuristic evaluation concept. The criteria are in line with the developments in the second iteration period.

2.2.4 Evaluation Criteria

The following criteria represent a means of measure established to assess the degree to which SatisFactory solutions are able to meet the objectives. For this purpose, the combined evaluation methodology described in the previous sections is translated into five criteria:

- Usability
- Knowledge integration
- Perception of working experience
- User acceptance
- Impact of SatisFactory

Such criteria are translated into KPIs, which can be furtherly grouped into three main groups, such as *Satisfaction Indicators*, *Business Facilitation Indicators*, and *Ease of Use Indicators* (Section 2.2.5). More details will be given in the next sections.

2.2.4.1 Usability

Usability is one of the most widely used tools for assessing the perceived usability of a product by a user. It is a broad term that incorporates better graphical representation of simulation input and output, simple navigation and flexible control, as well as suitability for the respective address use. Appropriately combining and visualising all types and levels of information involved in industrial manufacturing processes is undoubtedly a heavily complex task.

To do so, SatisFactory has to support a series of visualisation, incident management and decision support components and techniques appropriate for the process operators and supervisors. Within our project, the design and exploitation of user-centric technologies

represent the main aspect of this work. Hence, the usability criterion aims to evaluate the suitability and the effect on the shop floor, shifting the focus on the user work experience rather than on the product. Moreover, the technologies and tools introduced will be assessed in terms of level of learnability and applicability.

2.2.4.2 Knowledge Integration

The information that flows within the shop floor is immense. Real-time data from the sensorial system, manuals, standard operating procedures, emergency operating procedures, standard guidelines, customised requirements and specification and so on represent the variety both size and type. This immense knowledge needs to be integrated and filtered, in order to provide to each worker what is necessary, when it is necessary.

With Knowledge Integration we want to assess how the information is integrated through the implementation of semantic models. Such models put the foundations for a semantically enriched environment where the shop floor knowledge is gathered, processed and shared. Moreover, Knowledge Integration refers to the evaluation of the exploitation of the shop floor knowledge, in the way that the shop floor activities are supported or that this knowledge is translated, managed, and then exposed through the SatisFactory platform. It is also noted that the developed framework will deliver different views of information depending on the organisational level and localisation of the end-users, which is also a parameter to be considered in the evaluation.

2.2.4.3 Perception of working experience

The purpose of this criterion is to gain feedback from workers and decision makers about the value of their work experience. Social and environmental aspects of the end-user working experience will be investigated in order to obtain the workers' point of view. Among the aspects to be evaluated from the end-user, it's worth mentioning: work organisation, attitude of the other workers, ergonomics, safety, quality of training and assistance. The perception of the user's working experience is about motivations, attitudes, expectations, behavioural patterns and constraints. It is about the types of interactions people have, how they feel about an experience, and what actions they expect to take (Pavliscak, 2014).

The introduction of gamification and collaboration tools, the use of AR-based devices change the work environment and certainly influence the perception of the working experience. For example, the revolution of the training environment through the introduction of AR devices and semantic technologies is a relevant aspect of this evaluation criterion. In this context, the development of an on-job training platform requires the assessment of the training outcomes from the user point of view. This may include the evaluation of many aspects, such as, the effectiveness of the training methods and materials used; the relevance of the training content; the knowledge, attitudes and skills gained by the trainees.

2.2.4.4 User acceptance

The user acceptance is defined as the willingness within a user group (workers or decision makers) to employ new technologies for the tasks they are designed to support. Thus, such concept is not being applied to situations in which users claim they will employ it without providing evidence of use, or to the use of a technology for purposes unintended by the designers or procurers. From the evaluation point of view the end point is to verify that the

solution provided works for the user. Therefore, the user acceptance criterion has been defined in order to create reasonable metrics for evaluating the acceptance of the technologies introduced by SatisFactory within the industrial partners' shop floor.

It is stressed that the user acceptance will not be evaluated only within the scope and the duration of the project, but also as the willingness of the involved stakeholders to embrace and reuse the developed tools in their everyday activities. The extension of the use of SatisFactory tools to more processes and operations after the project duration is what we consider an interesting potential.

2.2.4.5 Impact of SatisFactory

This criterion aims to assess the overall impact of SatisFactory within the specific pilot sites, and then, in the aspects that span across the 5 objectives from a more general perspective. Different aspects of the SatisFactory impact, e.g. Economic, Management, Design and the like, will become a common base for a set of performance indicators. From the satisfaction point of view, the reduction of time for operations and frequency of system's failures might be two meaningful aspects to evaluate. Instead, from the business facilitation point of view, financial aspects such as cost of installation and maintenance or ROI can be also meaningful toward the definition of a set of KPIs for this general purpose criterion.

In the Impact of SatisFactory criterion we aim to assess the overall feeling and added value that the framework leaves to the end users. In a sense we wish to evaluate how much of a change, impact the tools and components, as well as the entire framework have on the daily activities and the satisfaction and well-being of the workers. A considerable impact will facilitate adoption and extension of usage.

2.2.5 Performance Indicators

In this section the performance indicators to be used are presented, according to the criteria and categories discussed in the previous sections. The performance indicators have been revisited in the second iteration period and they represent the final form for the SatisFactory project.

2.2.5.1 Usability

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Usability	Satisfaction Indicators	
	U1	Effectiveness of tasks completed using the SatisFactory framework
	U2	Percentage of reduction of time on a single task
	U3	Percentage of reduction of failures
	U4	Percentage of correct identification of incidents at the shop floor
	U5	Number of operators using the suggestion platform
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	U6	Percentage of successful re-adaptation and appropriate work assignment to actors
	U7	Number of identified areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks
	U8	Provision of straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status
	Ease of Use Indicators	
U9	Variety of visualisations offered	
U10	Percentage of workers feeling motivated and playful	
U11	Facilitation of task performance	

2.2.5.2 Knowledge Integration

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Knowledge Integration	Satisfaction Indicators	
	KI1	Percentage of appropriate/suitable data/information received
	KI2	Percentage of on time delivery of data/information
	KI3	Reduced average time for completion of training procedures

	KI4	Number of submitted suggestions
	KI5	Number of collaboration actions through the platform
	KI6	Identification of patterns of workers' movement at the shop floor
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	KI7	Reduction of errors related to accurate localisation of information and/or objects in the shop floor
	KI8	Number of accepted suggestions
	KI9	Reduction of time for training procedures preparation
	KI10	Training cost reduction
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	KI11	Percentage of availability of efficient information through AR tools
	KI12	Percentage of provision of unreadable and incomprehensible data/information

2.2.5.3 Perception of working experience

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Working Experience	Satisfaction Indicators	
	WE1	Percentage of demonstration of safety procedures and ergonomics through the platform
	WE2	Usefulness/Improvement of training sessions for knowledge and skills enrichment
	WE3	Percentage of workers that used the AR components
	WE4	Percentage of workers that would reuse the AR components
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	WE5	Continuous automatic monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras
	WE6	Increase of safety at work due to usage of SatisFactory tools
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	WE7	Reduction in the number of requests for help to other workers/experts
	WE8	Provision of complete and reliable training
	WE9	Reduction of work-related stress

2.2.5.4 User acceptance

Criterion	ID	Indicator
User Acceptance	Satisfaction Indicators	
	UA1	Level of user engagement
	UA2	Level of applicability of lessons learned to everyday activities
	UA3	Percentage of successful access to data/information through AR platform
	UA4	Level of engagement of operators using the suggestion platform (>3 suggestions per year)
	UA5	Level of engagement of operators using the collaboration platform (>3 collaborations per year)
	Business Facilitation Indicators	
	UA6	Reduction of process or machine downtime
	UA7	Number of SOP transformed into AR tools
	UA8	Level of improved sense of team spirit
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	UA9	Reduction of misinterpretations
UA10	Increased attractiveness using gamification tools	
UA11	Percentage of workers feeling participating into a user community, having novel ways for social interaction and communication	
UA12	Percentage of positive feedbacks from operators	

2.2.5.5 Impact of SatisFactory

Criterion	ID	Indicator
Impact	Satisfaction Indicators	
	OI1	Incidents handled by the SF System
	OI2	Overall satisfaction regarding tool's features and functionality
	OI3	Frequency of the failures of the system
	Business Facilitation Indicators	

	O14	Cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance
	O15	Return on Investment (ROI)
	O16	Criticality of the failures of the system
	Ease of Use Indicators	
	O17	Level of applicability of SatisFactory tools
	O18	Fit for purpose (the tool is fulfilling the expressed needs and it fits for the purpose it was developed)
	O19	Level of overall aesthetic attractiveness to the end users

3. SATISFACTORY PILOT SITES (AREA ANALYSIS AND DESIGN)

3.1 CERTH/CPERI

3.1.1 Description of selected pilot areas

CERTH/CPERI has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). Also Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software, with OPC connectivity. CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485). Within the project, CERTH/CPERI will utilise its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI's process plants where the Industrial Lab cases will take place. Also CERTH/CPERI's selected shop-floor processes will be used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions. CERTH/CPERI's infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

CERTH/CPERI shop floor view (1)

CERTH/CPERI shop floor view (2)

Figure 3 CERTH/CPERI shop floor view

Pilot plants produce each day real-time data stored in repositories that provide a significant amount of information currently analysed using conventional tools while the decision making

relies on information which is compiled in a manual manner by the process operators and the process supervisors. Besides the collection, analysis and deployment of automated actions, the aforementioned infrastructure is equipped with data visualization tools combined with content aware functions using diagnosis and alarm triggering tools. The user interacts with the devices, the sensors and the actuators through a set of user-friendly human machine interfaces (HMI) that provide the basis for the decision making process in real-time. Furthermore, the data can be accessed by local or remote information points and can be managed by supervisory functions. Thus, the operators can intuitively understand the status and the various conditions of the process equipment and respond accordingly upon demand. The aforementioned infrastructure is developed using a set of adaptive user interfaces combined with flexible sensor topologies that are able to tackle the heterogeneity of the various devices which are present in a smart factory.

3.1.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

One of the main operational constraints of CERTH/CPERI is related to safety, material handling and timely performance of operational procedures. All the processes on the shop floor include chemical and other sensitive materials which require special handling regarding safety. In order to avoid incidents or accidents, the safety measures are very specific and strict (according to ISO standards, e.g. 9001) and all workers must be cautious and follow the procedures carefully. Also the material handling defines a set of constraints related to the treatment of specific substances (chemicals in liquid, gas or solid state) during the preparation or the operation of the process units.

Besides the internal operational constraints related to the procedures performed at the process units, there are a set of constraints related to the relationship and the sharing of information with the clients. This means that any data that has been categorized as confidential is not allowed to be distributed outside of the internal ICT infrastructures of CERTH/CPERI and provided to third parties. This information is about technical schematics, instrumentation diagrams, process documents, financial data, new developments, customer details, reference bill of materials (process and electrical BOMs), production plans etc.

Regarding legal constraints, all workers of CERTH/CPERI sign a confidentiality agreement regarding the procedures, the infrastructure and the data (experimental or theoretical) that are produced from the plant floor procedures and plant operation. The produced data (raw signals from the field or processed data) are to be handled as need to know basis and are distributed according to the respective contracts as signed per customer. The analytical data are covered by the confidentiality and quality assurance procedures described by the respective ISO (9001 or 17025).

3.2 SUNLIGHT

3.2.1 Description of selected pilot areas

Sunlight has several production lines, applying different manufacturing processes in each production stage. Two of them have been selected to be the pilot areas in which the

SatisFactory components will be installed and tested. The first one is the battery cell formation process (jar formation), which is the last stage of the PzS batteries production line and the second one is Motive power (traction) batteries assembly line.

- **Jar Formation pilot area**

The initial formation charge of a lead-acid battery, whether in the form of plates or as an already assembled battery, is quite a complex bundle of chemical reactions. It is important to know in principle about the most important parameters controlling this process in order to achieve good reproducible results with reasonable efforts.

Jar formation is applied to already assembled battery cells. In the Jar formation area there are Battery formation modules which are circulating the electrolyte through each battery cell. The formation process for the battery cells begins with the filling process. The battery cells are connected to the battery formation modules which are responsible to fill and circulate the electrolyte in to the cells and the battery charger which are performing the formation process. The time gap between electrolyte filling and the initiation of the formation process is critical. If the formation starts immediately after filling, a significant amount of acid may remain unreacted. There are several formation algorithms and profiles that can be applied. Several conditions must be considered for applying the most proper formation profile.

Figure 4 Battery formation modules with Acid circulation

- **Motive power (Traction) battery assembly**

Sunlight Motive power batteries can cover all types of motive power needs, from light duty single-shift operation to heavy duty multi-shift operations, and are suitable for all industrial electric forklift types, such as counterbalanced, narrow aisle and hand trucks. The Motive Power battery assembly line is a manual assembly line.

The Motive Power battery assembly procedure includes the following stages:

- Cells fitting into metal tray. With the use of load manipulator, each cell is placed into metal tray according to battery's model. Each battery model has different type of cells and tray.

- Inspection level electrolyte. If the level of electrolyte is not proper, electrolyte is filled or removed according to the need. An automatic valve specially designed for the aforementioned procedure, helps the workers to fulfil the procedure avoiding injuries due to electrolytes acidity.
- Battery cleaning. The metal tray and battery cells must be carefully cleaned. Electrolyte is strong acid and contact must be avoided. Furthermore, the final product must look clean and shiny.
- Connectors fitting. In this step, the cells are being connected together with cables and bolts to form a battery. During the procedure, workers have the connections schematic available in order to avoid mistakes, because connections are different to each battery model.
- Inspection bolts and voltage. To warranty the good functionality of a battery. The bolts must be tight and each cell must have 2 volts. Concerning the functionality of a battery, this is the final check.
- Labels fitting. The label of SUNLIGHT, caution labels and function labels are added. Labels help end users to avoid injuries and also, to transfer and install the battery properly. All the labels are stickers on the metal tray.
- Advisories & appurtenances fitting. The end user may choose to add some extra components to the battery (e.g. electrolyte level indicator, voltage indicator). These components are added at this step. Furthermore, the user manual is attached during this step.
- Palletizing & packing with nylon. The battery, before the despatch for the warehouse, is being palletized and packed with nylon in order to avoid scratches and protect batteries during transfer.

Figure 5 Sunlight Motive Power Battery

(a)

(b)

Figure 6 Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line

3.2.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

The operational constraints that are applied in Sunlight concern not only the production itself but also the relationship with the customers and between employees. One of the main principle at Sunlight is the strict adhering to all health and safety as well as environmental regulations for all production lines, including the selected as pilot areas. For this reason there are important rules which are mandatory for all employees and apply to the entire territory of the plant and production areas. Concerning the quality, there are also particular constrains that are applied to each production stage. All these operations are performed according to the international standards (ISO 9001, ISO 14001, BS OHSAS 18001) that are already installed in Sunlight.

Legal constrains are enforced to the employees related with the confidential information that they handle in each case. This means that any data that has been categorized as confidential is not allowed to be exported from the company and provided to third parties. This information can be technical documents, financial data, new developments, client lists and details, reference lists, production plans etc.

3.3 COMAU

3.3.1 Description of selected pilot areas

COMAU is a global supplier of industrial automation systems for the automotive manufacturing sector and a global provider of full maintenance services. To the “automotive” Customers worldwide, COMAU offers its capacity as “System Integrator” and its complete engineering solutions, from product development to the realization of industrial process automation systems. COMAU provides also integrated services to the manufacturing plants, from assistance to the production start-up phases, up to equipment and plant full maintenance activities. COMAU comprises the following organizational units: Body Assembly, Powertrain Systems, Robotics & Service, Adaptive Solutions. The continuous improvement of products, processes and services, through the application of the most advanced innovative technological solutions, allows COMAU to contribute to its Customers’ competitive advantage. Research and development activities are aimed primarily at the evolution of technologies applied to manufacturing systems, but also to the creation of a company portfolio in terms of standardised product/process solutions, in order to improve the overall competitiveness of the production of the company’s affiliates.

Within the SatisFactory Project mainly two of the organizational units are involved: Robotics and Body Assembly.

- **Robotics: robot wrist assembly**

In the robotics business unit the robot assembly is an operation performed completely by hand. The robot arm is composed by several main sub-components (i.e. base, forearm, arm, wrist), each of them is assembled in a specific “Operating Station”.

Each station is equipped with a specific set of tools, power-tools and parts that allows the operator to perform the assembly operations, working in the best conditions in terms of movements, lighting, components reach, etc. in other words from the ergonomic point of view.

Within the SatisFactory Project, the most representative assembly phase analyzed is the wrist assembly. This operation is critical because for different robot families, the internal components are similar, but with little variations, that mean different assembly procedures. The operators are usually dedicated to specific sub-assembly operations, thus they know very well the right sequence of operations, but sometimes they are requested to move in different places in order to replace colleagues or to face different products demands. Under these particular conditions, the operators’ workload is significantly increased because they need to readapt to a different production process.

In this case, a system able to support the operator with a step-by-step interactive manual could significantly reduce the risk of errors in the assembly procedures, while reducing the mental workload of the operator and improving the overall efficiency. Moreover, the introduction of digital tools like calipers, dynamometers, torque wrenches etc. will allow the system to produce automated checklists that certify also the quality of the product. This is actually done manually by means of modules filled by the operators.

Following in red is highlighted the component assembled in the reference Operating Station.

Figure 7 Robot wrist assembly

- **Body Assembly: remote assistance on robotized production cell**

Body assembly lines are very complex systems constituted by robotic arms, mechanical tools controlled by means of compressed air and transport systems electro-actuated. When a fault occurs, the maintenance staff is called by the operators and has to fix it in the shortest timeframe in order to avoid costly production losses. The main problem is that maintenance staff cannot always fix the problem alone, sometimes an external intervention or support is required from engineering or from skilled personnel not always available. In this case a support platform including tools that allow remote maintenance and collaboration as well as augmented reality could significantly reduce the MTTR (Mean Time To Repair) of the machines, allowing considerable savings.

Within the SatisFactory project a robotized production cell will be used as test bed in order to develop and test the aforementioned features.

The main components constituting the COMAU SatisFactory Test Cell are respectively an APC (Accumulating Pallet Conveyor) feeding system, two robots devoted to handling and welding functionalities and a tool-table. Hereafter a short description for each component shown is provided:

1. APC: it is a production line feeding system in charge of collecting elements and sub-assemblies built in external lines or coming from metal stamping, with the final goal of providing a continuous and automated elements availability to the production line. A central chain ring allows the pallets movement. Each pallet hosts a single element and, once it is removed by the robot, a synchronized stopper movement allows the pallet to “turn down” and reach again the beginning of the conveyor in order to be

filled again, while the next pallet makes a step forward and it again ready to fill the line with a new element.

2. Handling Robot: this subsystem is composed by a robot equipped with a gripper that includes clamps, centering pins and it is designed to move elements from/to different stations, transport systems or external feeding systems
3. Welding Robot: also named “Spot Welding Machine”, is a subsystem composed by a specific robot equipped with a spot welding gun. It can be easily customized in order to weld in the more appropriate way each metal sheet thickness, starting from two 0,5mm to three 1,4 mm metal parts.
4. Tool-table with fixtures and lock-pins, with the main function of holding in position the elements to be welded. This provides the right geometry to the finished car part.

These embedded systems are representative examples of complex devices that compose typically production lines in car body assembly processes.

Figure 8 Body Assembly

3.3.2 Legal and Operational Constraints

Main legal constraints in COMAU are related to the confidentiality of some data like financial data, new developments, client lists and details, production plans etc., as well as specific phases of the production process as well as the technical documents of the components (in some cases protected by means of international patents).

A second important group of constraints from the legal point of view is related to the interaction with labour unions. In this case, the application of novel technologies in the industrial environment like cameras, indoor localization systems, etc. could lead to privacy issues, as well as ergonomics issues, like the application of glasses for augmented reality, that is actually not normed, and a constant usage could cause problems not yet classified.

From the operational point of view, main constraints are related from one side to the production itself, from the other, like for SunLight the wide number of international standards and norms that machines and products must respect, as well as the adherence to the World Class Manufacturing program pillars (shown in the following picture), where COMAU is putting significant effort in order to improve the complete process chain.

Figure 9 World Class Manufacturing program pillars

4. EVALUATION PROCESS

In this Section the approach for the scenarios used in the evaluation framework is analysed. This approach has been revisited in the second iteration which led to minor updates mainly in ES3 and the respective data collection tools.

It should be kept in mind that the selected process aims to evaluate in essence the exploitable outcomes from the end user's point of view. The user experience in relation with the business scenarios that people are involved is considered. It is noted that there is a straightforward connection of the Business Scenarios (BSCs), Evaluation Scenarios (ESs), Evaluation Tests (ETs) and SatisFactory products. The list of the SatisFactory single technologies as depicted in D7.1.2 "Market Analysis and Exploitation Strategy" and its current status in the framework of T7.2 "Exploitation Strategy of SatisFactory exploitable products", as well as D1.2.3 "Use Case analysis and application scenarios description" are taken into account.

Table 2 SatisFactory products for evaluation

No	Exploitable product
1	Semantics and Context-aware knowledge shop floor analysis engine
2	Real-time localization of workers, tools and machines
3	Dynamic Re-adaptation of Production Facilities
4	HR workload balancing toolkit (Incident management)
5	Feedback Engine (incident detection)
6	On-the-job training toolkit
7	Hardware HMI, HMD
8	Integrated shop floor DSS
9	Gamification/Collaboration platform for manufacturing enterprises
10	Middleware for Smart Factories
11	Smart Sensor Network for Industrial Applications

The connection of the BSCs, ESs, ETs and SatisFactory products is shown in the following table, even if there is a partial connection to the BSCs. As it can be seen in section 2.2.5, there are KPIs aiming at the evaluation of specific products and this has been taken into account when forming the ETs. It is noted that products 10: Middleware for Smart Factories and 11: Smart Sensor Network for Industrial Applications are in essence part of the evaluation for all ETs, even though they are in the background and their involvement may be small in some cases.

Table 3 connection of the BSCs, ESs, ESs, ETs and SatisFactory products

ET	BSC CPERI	BSC COMAU	BSC SUNLIGHT	SatisFactory products
ET1: Automated Support for Assembly Operations	BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-3.1	1, 3, 5, 8, 10, 11
ET2: AR supported assembly operations	BSC-5.2	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-4.1	1, 2, 6, 7, 10
ET3: Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	BSC-5.1	BSC-2.1	BSC-3.1	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 10, 11
ET4: Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing	BSC-5.3	BSC-2.1	BSC-3.1	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 10
ET5: Collaboration in Shop Floor Working Environment	BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-3.1 BSC-4.1?	1, 9, 10, 11
ET6: Supporting recognition of incidents in equipment/ operations	BSC-5.1	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-4.2	1, 2, 3, 10, 11
ET7: Recognition of Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor	BSC-6.1	BSC1-1, BSC-1.2		1, 2, 3, 10, 11
ET8: On-the-job training in assembly operations	BSC-5.2	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-4.3	1, 6, 7, 10
ET9: Gamification in Shop Floor Working Environment	BSC-5.1, BSC-5.3	BSC-1.1, BSC-1.2	BSC-3.1, BSC-4.1, BSC-4.3	1, 9, 10, 11

4.1 EVALUATION SCENARIOS (ES)

The evaluation of the SatisFactory components, key exploitable products and the overall framework takes into account the Business Scenarios that have been developed as a result of the efforts of T1.1 End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications, T1.2 Models for actors and procedures interconnection and T1.3 Use Cases and Scenarios. The BSCs have been updated and improved and this has been depicted in the final iterations of D1.1 User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and deployment guidelines and D1.2 Use Case analysis and application scenarios and descriptions.

In an attempt to simplify the evaluation procedure and in order for it to be valuable to other BSCs and processes which are not part of the SatisFactory analysis, the Evaluation Scenarios are perceived and designed to be usable during and after the duration of the project. They are tied to the BSCs in the sense that they are realised in them by grouping common KPIs, process steps, tools and applications used, tasks required to be implemented by the workers etc. They are also tied to the evaluation objectives and criteria as they derived from them, in attempt to evaluate the overall impact of the SatisFactory framework. It is noted that, as the BSCs have been revisited, the same was done for the corresponding Evaluation Scenarios and the associated Evaluation Tests.

4.1.1 Evaluation Scenario ES1: Supporting Assembly Operations

The assembly operations have been identified as of critical importance, as they can be individual tasks or a set of steps in a broader task that workers need to undertake. They are common in automotive and heavy equipment industries, electronics, defence, aerospace, telecommunications, power & automation, energy & resource, naval engineering, as it has also been defined by AREA. The scope of this evaluation scenario is to support the workers in carrying out assembly operations by providing them the required information using real-time localisation, AR, DSS, information from the automation system and SOP, depending on the use case to be studied and implemented.

4.1.1.1 ES1.1 Automated support for assembly operations

In this evaluation scenario, the worker is prompt to **perform assembly operations** in a standardised way. The layout is relatively stable, in the sense that the working stations are set and the worker performs the steps in a defined manner. However, different products require different set of materials and tools to be identified and selected, a series of manual movements to be conducted in a certain way, exact points to be sought and identified etc. A successful support automatically suggests the adaptation of the specific steps to be performed, feeds the information to the **HR workbalance toolkit** and provides the worker with the **required information** and visualisation tools to complete the task.

Addressed requirements

The main goal is to address the multiple challenges in the assembly operations and help the workers by facilitating the provision of information and resources to respond in time and effectively.

The evaluation process considers the aspects required for the successful completion of an assembly task. The on time acknowledgment of the requirement to take up such a task comes first and then the assignment of the suitable worker in term of skills and availability follows. This procedure results to a notification for a specific worker to carry out a specific task using a specific set of tools. Hence, a number of evaluation tests are performed to assess among others the reduction of assembly faults while increasing ergonomics, convenience and worker satisfaction.

4.1.1.2 ES1.2 AR supported assembly operations

In the AR supported assembly operations evaluation scenario the worker is required to perform an assembly operation using an **AR SOP Presentation Tool**. The main issue lies in the aspect of customised customer requirements and the need to pay special attention to certain steps of the procedure for **safety reasons**. Although the actual **assembly** is done using up to a certain degree an automated system, attention needs to be given to the **ergonomy** and safety features also.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of this scenario is to address the automatic assembly operations, so as to enable efficient and error-free task fulfilment since the aspect of customisation which emerges quite often increases the difficulty of carrying out the steps required.

The main perspective in the evaluation scenario is to address user satisfaction related to the performance of the provided tools (localisation, AR, recommendations given, assignments made etc.). Thus, a number of evaluation tests is performed taking also into account knowledge sharing, provision of valuable feedback on effective operations. To this end, the support in the decision making concerning the effective workload, resources management and with visual tools is also evaluated.

4.1.2 Evaluation Scenario ES2: Offering Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing Services

The scope is to evaluate the services offered related to maintenance (corrective and preventive), re-adaptation and HR workload balancing through the SatisFactory framework. These services are required for the efficient operation at the shop floor, to ensure that the equipment is up and running in order to fulfil production needs, to ensure the safety of the workers at the shop floor level, to reduce the work related stress and to efficiently manage human resources.

4.1.2.1 ES2.1 Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing

In this evaluation scenario, a **failure in equipment** occurs and the incident is detected, the work allocation is suggested as well as the **re-adaptation of the scheduling**. Moreover, the worker prompted to respond to take action is provided with the set of tools and **information required to perform the task** and he/she is able to collaborate with others who have taken care of similar work orders and to take advantage of their experiences.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation scenario is to address malfunctions and failures in a well-defined and more automated way. All involved stakeholders at different operational levels can view information about the occurring incident and the workers at the shop floor are guided with the appropriate set of tools and information to address the task.

A malfunction detected by the automation system occurs and it reaches the iDSS through the Middleware. iDSS evaluates the input and suggests a course of actions, as well as the necessary resources for it. Therefore, the evaluation scenario addresses user satisfaction in timely and suitable notification, the timely mitigation actions suggested, the quality of the provided tools and guidelines etc. A number of evaluation tests are performed according to the description in Annex IV.

4.1.2.2 ES2.2 Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing

In this evaluation scenario a **preventive maintenance** program has been scheduled and it is in turn to be realised. The **prioritisation of activities** is important, as well as the work scheduling, allowing for the complete preventive maintenance action to take place. The work allocation is suggested based on available resources taking into consideration that re-adaptation may be needed. The **worker** assigned to perform the task is provided with the tools and information required and is also **informed on the SOP to be followed**.

Addressed requirements

The main goal is to address the preventive maintenance actions, required to ensure that the shop floors are up and running. Apart from the details related to the exact BSCs, operating using preventive maintenance as a main activity has a positive effect also on the sense of safety and satisfaction of the workers.

A preventive maintenance action needs to be implemented, according to the schedules and plans of the Production and Maintenance departments. The planned aspect of the action may allow for scheduling flexibility, which is considered by the re-adaptation and HR workload management toolkit. Moreover, this flexibility, along with the information of resources required to complete the task are processed by the iDSS which provides suggestions on prioritisation and optimal series of actions. The information is conveyed to the involved workers via the Shopfloor Feedback Engine.

4.1.3 Evaluation Scenario ES3: Supporting Incident Detection & Recognition Operations

The scope of this evaluation scenario is to monitor the real working environment under normal or extraordinary conditions in order to detect and recognize incidents with equipment or humans that may happen or have just occurred. In this case, a number of different sensors will be utilized, such as depth sensors, thermal cameras, wearable localization sensors, etc. depending on the use case and the incidents that the SatisFactory is interested in.

4.1.3.1 ES3.1: Supporting recognition of incidents in equipment/operations

In this evaluation scenario, the recognition of incidents in equipment and/or operations at the shopfloor is supported. A successful support is the one that **automatically monitors** a process, **on-the-fly checks** the real-life data at real-time, **detects potential problems** and **sends alert** to specified users (employees responsible for this process).

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to automatically address malfunctions in equipment by detecting them and to inform on-time the end-user, so as to make the necessary actions.

As part of the impact assessment analysis, the evaluation process will take into account both functional and non-functional requirements, since the optimal operation of the system will affect the on-time problem notification to the end-user, the timely mitigation actions, the accuracy (versus to corresponding manual operation) and the saved man hours and effort. Thus, a number of evaluation tests are going to be performed to this end as they described at Annex IV.

4.1.3.2 ES3.2: Recognizing Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor

In this evaluation scenario, the human movements in the shop-floor are going to be monitored, in order to detect and recognize incidents where humans are involved. **Incidents** like human falls, collisions, etc. will be **detected** either proactive or reactive. In any case, the end-users are going to be on-time informed (**send alerts** or **warnings**), for their timely

mitigation actions. Furthermore, the system will provide/distribute safe **optimized paths** to the workers for specific zones and hours so as to minimize the frequency of the incidents.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the scenario is to address automatic detection of the incidents that involve humans, so as to make the necessary actions. Optimal paths are going to be provided to the end-users.

Therefore, the main perspective of this evaluation scenario is to address user satisfaction and acceptance related to the issues concerning incidents, such as the on-time end-user notification, the timely mitigation actions in case of an incident, the number of proactive incidents that are prevented, the quality of the suggested paths, the number of incidents occurred on the suggested paths, etc. Thus, a number of evaluation tests are performed to this end as described at Annex IV.

4.1.4 Evaluation Scenario ES4: Offering “On-the-Job” Training Services

One assumption in Satisfactory is that the AR technologies (and part of related data) that are applied in the assistance to the worker during his/her normal work (i.e. mounting activities and verify the results), can be the same used during the “on-the-job” training activities.

Many studies proved that assembly applications can benefit substantially from the improved memorization attainable via AR and, the improved memorization can shorten the training time of new employees. Enhancement of long-term memory is also a strong positive factor in the understanding and retention of assembly or repair sequences, procedures and other information. More information can be found in D2.5 “On-the-job” training/educational environment and D4.3 Interactive augmented reality environment.

4.1.4.1 ES4.1 Training environment set-up

The approach is similar to the set-up of the environment for the guidance during the Mounting phase when the AR supporting tool is set-up.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the scenario is to address the creation of the environment for support to the worker during the mounting activity. The objective of the evaluation is to verify the ability to support the trainee through effective multimodal HMI. In particular, main issues addressed are:

- Flexibility in describing the specific training procedures in the various selected BSC;
- Flexibility to easily change the description of such procedures for improving the effectiveness of the training by introducing specific and / or critical situations;
- Existence of full support to the description of procedures based on conditional constructs, as well as on pre-conditions to test or implement in order to safely perform a specific procedure;
- Ability to manage the many types of content to the basis of the description of the training procedures (e.g. Documents, Pictures, Videos, CAD models, etc.) and automatically create new ones in order to enrich the information content provided to the trainee (e.g. 3D animations, audio clips, video clips, etc.);

- Possibility of the solutions used in describing the training procedures, to make automatic part of such description, based on the capture on-the-job-specific data (e.g. Data from motion capture, object recognition, sensor / device-based, etc.)

4.1.4.2 ES4.2 Training support – Execution

The execution stage regards the support to the worker during the on-the job activity. The guidance will be contextualized with the action.

Addressed requirements

Main requirements in this ES are:

- The ability to monitor and control (to the extent made available by the state of the technology) the procedures performed by the trainee, in order to immediately report or made available for subsequent analysis, anomalies, errors and / or specific triggered events;
- The ability to raise additional information to the main ones proposed by the system;
- Ability of the trainee to talk to his supervisor and/or instructors, in order to receive help and / or specific directions to follow.

4.1.4.3 ES4.3 Training support – Data Analysis

In this phase, the results obtained during the execution are analysed. The tool creates comparisons with previously accumulated data and provides input for the individual or trainee groups statistical analysis.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process addresses:

- Ability to process efficiently the data accumulated during the training, whether they are related to the execution time, the events generated by the system in case of anomalies and errors, voluntarily by the operator generated events (e.g. interruption);
- Ability to present the accumulated data and those derived effectively, focusing on visual representations for easy reference.

4.1.5 Evaluation Scenario ES5: Gamification and Collaboration Tools Usage

The scope of this scenario is to evaluate how much SatisFactory tools increase the satisfaction of workers. This is evaluated on the basis of two aspects: Collaboration and Gamification. The aim of the collaboration tool is to improve the social collaboration between workers and as a consequence to result in better satisfaction. The aim of the gamification tool is to motivate unpopular tasks better and as a consequence, to decrease dissatisfaction.

4.1.5.1 ES5.1: Gamification Tools Usage

In this evaluation scenario, workers can collect points by performing certain tasks. These can be unpopular actions, like washing the hands in order to clean them from lead before having a break or going to canteen, but also popular/accepted actions like the submission of a suggestion for improvement points or an AR training session. The cumulative points of the groups are publicly displayed with the goal to beat the group result of the former day (win streak approach). At the same time, each worker can access his individual points on which basis he can achieve better avatars, badges or company rewards.

As far as Social Collaboration is concerned, there are gamified procedures that are deployed on pre-pilot and pilot plants where workers can achieve points, badges and level up as well. In order to gain the gamification awards one should use the Tips&Tricks section so as to start gaining points by making questions and answering to existing ones. Additionally, voting for a useful answer or for an important question are gamified actions that offer points. Furthermore, in order to achieve a badge, a certain amount of points should be gained in order to unlock the award. These kinds of awards are also applied in general posting of material in the Social Collaboration platform as well as when liking and commenting on material uploaded by others or even when performing a training session using the AR Training Platform which correspond to actions defined in a relevant gamified scenario. Similarly, every level defined in a game has a starting limit measured by points, which when reached, the worker scales up to it.

All gamified actions are combined with the aforementioned awards, points, badges and levels, via rules which determine how many points will be gained from triggered actions and afterwards at which point badges and levels are achieved. Important notice is that some badges are available only for once so as to be evaluated as rare ones and moreover, every awards of type badge can be achieved up to a certain amount so as avoid overdoing it with specific behaviors. A successful support is the one that increases the number of performed unpopular actions and that increases the overall worker satisfaction.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to check whether worker satisfaction is improved with regard to unpopular tasks. These are all tasks which are considered as being annoying, for example, because they reduce the time of their breaks.

Particular requirements for unpopular tasks have been identified with regards to dealing with risks, dangers and emergencies in general (Requirement SAFA-156), with washing hands to clean them from lead every time the shop-floor is left in particular (Requirement SAFA-87) and with the training of new production processes (Requirement SAFA-80). Also, especially younger generation people have been identified as target group (Requirement SAFA-62). An

identified main driver for satisfaction at work is self-determination. This includes that people should be encouraged instead of forced for conducting unpopular actions.

Another identified driver is to see the own success and contribution to a team result. Finally, a safe environment and co-workers who show their awareness of safety issues is a driver for worker satisfaction.

To conclude, two kinds of evaluation tests are performed for this. Firstly, it is checked whether the number of performed unpopular actions has increased. Secondly, the workers' user experience with the system is assessed. This is described in Annex IV.

4.1.5.2 ES5.2: Collaboration Tools Usage

This scenario evaluates whether the collaboration between workers and managers can be improved by installing a support tool for suggestions for improvement process. Workers can submit suggestions for improvement (e.g. process improvements, wellbeing), which are sent to a decider and the decider's decision and justification is returned. The advantage of such a system in comparison to a paper-based version is that meeting the process worker – decider – worker is ensured. A successful support is the one that increases the satisfaction of workers with the suggestions for improvement system.

Moreover, in the Social Collaboration tool both workers and managers can benefit from its use. Benefits consist of a more pleasant and friendly environment where exchange of knowledge will pass from experienced employees to new ones, easily via online communication. Users participate in Social Collaboration platform in order to create an online community where they share same interests, common issues and get support by their co-workers during work in order to minimize mistakes. Through the use of the platform, users have the possibility to interact with co-workers in order to take guidelines and discuss possible problems in order to avoid malfunctions during training. Additionally, a Questions & Answers tool is available for the users to increase their knowledge and enhance their skills. This tool helps the creation of a knowledge database, where questions have already been asked and answered, as well as rated from co-workers denoting the most useful ones. This platform additionally is supported by gamification concepts in order to create a more attractive environment for employees.

The social collaboration platform is used by the workers in order to interact with co-workers by share knowledge to less experienced co-workers and asking for knowledge the more experienced ones. Furthermore, they enrich knowledge and have continuously access to stored knowledge database and best practices gathered in Tips&Tricks section. There is a continuously reforming of a documentation according to the needs of the industry so as to be helpful for every department in it. It provides ways of expressing different opinions for best practices, and reminders for practising skills and learning new procedures by using other tools. Social Collaboration tool also supports posting of text/ video and photos either public or private as well as exchanging multimedia context through messaging. In order to evaluate this tool as successful, increase of satisfaction and convenience has to be noticed among workers and employers.

Addressed requirements

The main goal of the evaluation process is to check whether worker satisfaction is improved with regard to the suggestions for improvement system. This is one paradigm of how the social collaboration between workers (shopfloor workers and managers) can be improved.

Several requirements for suggestions for improvement system have been identified. First of all, having a process for suggestions for improvement was considered valuable at all places, no matter if it already existed or not (Requirement SAFA-105). Then, in current systems, it was criticized that the submitter often does not get feedback of what happened to his suggestions, which leads to demotivation (Requirement SAFA-146). Finally, there is the need from the decider side to discuss the issues with co-workers (Requirement SAFA-97). Identified drivers for satisfaction at work, which are supported with the suggestions for improvement system are carriage of responsibility, being valued, diversity in work tasks, breaking monotony in mind, being trusted, seeing the own contribution to the work and the ability to help others. Thus, the workers' user experience with the system is assessed as described in Annex IV.

4.2 EVALUATION PLANNING

In the previous sections the methodological approach was described, as well as the pilot sites and the Generalised Evaluation Scenarios that will make use of the presented criteria and Key Performance Indicators. In this Section we answer to the question: "How is this evaluation plan going to be implemented?"

First of all, the planning procedure gave the focus and working groups a chance to better examine and evaluate their day-to-day activities, in terms of horizontal interconnections with other processes and operations, definition of drivers and decision making factors and departments, as well as expectations from the shop floor level regarding the features of the tools made available to them. This first step was the preparation process for the system evaluation. It is noted that this was the first step of the procedure and that two iterations followed, which allowed for amelioration and tuning.

The second step within this effort is actually the collection of feedback from the workers and the decision makers, which will also be completed in three iterations, as described below. In order to achieve that, dedicated workshops are organised and specific tools are used for the collection of data. The plan foresees two data collections at each shop floor; one after the first iteration of the deployment and another after the completion of the demonstrators.

4.2.1 Evaluation Workshops

The scope of the workshops is to inform the involved personnel that need to coordinate the data collection from the three shop floors in the adopted approach and to demonstrate the usage of the tools to be used. These workshops are performed in the form of webinars. It is imperative that the objectives and the message behind this effort pass through, in order to reach the required engagement. Dedicated meetings with individual end users may also follow, in order to provide more information and details if needed. It is noted that the involved partners support the end users throughout the process and additional guidance is provided before each workshop.

The procedure is planned as follows:

- First, the T5.2 presents the tools and trains the representatives of the end users that are designated to coordinate the data collection from the three shop floors.

- The next step in the deployment of the evaluation is that the trained representatives organise information sessions, either in the form of briefing of smaller teams or as collective info-sessions. In these sessions:
 - o the overall approach of the SatisFactory framework is presented,
 - o the scope and goal of the evaluation procedure is communicated and
 - o the participants are reminded of the Business Scenarios that they are being involved.
 - o Moreover, the Workers' Questionnaires are presented to the corresponding personnel, as well as the
 - o the Decision Makers' Questionnaires and the
 - o the Impact Check List respectively.
- Afterwards, and within a week from the information sessions, the data are collected, if not simultaneously.
- The data are then analysed by the involved partners,
- conclusions will be drawn and
- feedback is provided to the partners and development teams affected by the drawn results.

The three Workshops have been planned as follows.

4.2.1.1 1st Evaluation Workshop

The 1st Workshop is tied to *T5.3 Deployment of the Industry lab use case*, whose first iteration runs in the period M14-M16. Representatives from all the shop floors participated, to get an insight on the methodology and approach. It was planned to take place in the period end of M15 to beginning of M16, i.e. mid-March to mid-April 2016. The actual date that it took place was 19.05.2016, i.e. mid M17, to facilitate the participation of all partners. The instruments/tools developed can be found in Section 4.2.2 and their presentation during the Workshop was the activity related to *T5.2 Evaluation Methodology and Plans*.

The aforementioned timing has been initially selected, so that the deployment at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor will have progressed enough that the involved personnel could be able to provide an initial feedback on the SatisFactory tools used on site. The representatives of the Industrial pilot demonstrators took part in the 1st Workshop, mainly as observers, in order to follow the first implementation at the Industrial pilot, but also to provide feedback on the applicability of the procedure to their shop floors and any tuning that may be required. The goal is that process at CERTH/CPERI is evaluated and validated, in order to be used for the industrial pilots as well.

The results were analysed and shared with the partners involved in the technical workpackages, as they provided useful insight on the actual end users point of view and led to modifications in the development of the SatisFactory tools. The analysis of the results also served in the improvement of the instruments for the following Workshops.

The actual information session was initially planned to be conducted near the end of M16, early M17, when the preparation and the initial deployment would have reached its completion at CERTH/CPERI. It is noted that it was decided to combine the 1st information session with the 1st data collection on 08.06.2016, i.e. early M18.

4.2.1.2 2nd Evaluation Workshop

The 2nd Workshop is tied to the deployment at all shop floors serving as demonstrators in the SatisFactory project (*T5.3 Deployment of the Industry lab use case* and *T5.4 Industrial Pilot Demonstrators*). It was initially planned to take place in the period end of M23 to beginning of M24, i.e. mid-November to mid-December 2016. However, it was decided to allow for the completion of the second iteration of the integration (D5.1.2) due in M24, which led to the implementation of the 2nd Evaluation Workshop on 20.01.2017, i.e. mid M25. The logic is that on one hand, the implementation at the Industrial Lab running M22-M25 would be approaching to its completion and on the other hand implementation at the Industrial Pilots would have started, as the first iteration runs M22-M27.

Taking into consideration the revisited Business Scenarios and capitalising on the experience gained in the Industrial Lab deployment, the evaluation tools were revisited to adapt to the latest information made available. Moreover, in cooperation with *T5.1 Preparation and Component Integration to shopfloor* and *T5.5 Evaluation, Results Consolidation and Lessons Learned* the KPIs were also reconsidered.

The associated information sessions do not need to be conducted simultaneously at the shop floors. The exact dates were decided based on the availability of the developed tools, the application at the shop floors, the level of realisation of the Business Scenarios and the availability of the involved personnel that is required to take part in the evaluation procedure. The initial thought was to conduct the one at the Industrial Lab around M26 and at the Industrial Pilots around M30. For CERTH/CPERI the 2nd Information Session was again combined with the 2nd Data Collection on 25.01.2017 (M25). For SUNLIGHT the 1st Information Session took place on 12.06.2017 (i.e. mid M30) and the 1st Data Collection was held on 05.07.2017 (i.e. early M31). For COMAU the 1st Information Session took place simultaneously with the 1st Data Collection was held on 31.08.2017 (i.e. M32).

4.2.1.3 3rd Evaluation Workshop

The 3rd and last Workshop is tied to the implementation at the two Industrial Pilots (*T5.4 Industrial Pilot Demonstrators*), namely COMAU and SUNLIGHT. The second and last iteration of the deployment runs through M30-M35. The last iteration of *T5.2 Evaluation Methodology and Plans* runs M31-M32 and this is when the 3rd Evaluation Workshop has been planned. It capitalises on the knowledge gained from the completion of the deployment at the Industrial Lab (M22-M25) and the evaluation results from the 2nd Evaluation Workshop, as well as on the first deployment at the Industrial Pilots. This experience is also coupled with the results from the technical workpackages (WP1-WP4) which was concluded in M30.

Thus, the updated evaluation tools are used to account for all the changes made, the latest information available and the form of the SatisFactory framework. The aforementioned feedback has been exploited and the findings were translated into the Evaluation Scenarios that were presented in the 3rd Workshop, where end users participated. The representatives of the Industrial Lab demonstrator took part to share their experiences to the representatives from the Industrial Pilots and to provide feedback on the applicability of the procedure, any problems encountered and solutions they adopted. The participants from COMAU and SUNLIGHT were involved in the realisation of the evaluation information sessions that will follow. Again, these sessions do not need to run simultaneously, but according to each partner's availability and schedule. However, they will need to be completed within *T5.5*

Evaluation, Results Consolidation and Lessons Learned (M34-M36) and the results will be part of D5.5 Final System Evaluation Report (M36).

4.2.2 Instruments

The evaluation procedure makes use of the Evaluation Scenarios and Sub-scenarios which are linked to the Evaluation Tests. The Evaluation Tests, in turn, embrace and contain specific KPIs that are matched to the evaluation of specific SatisFactory exploitable outcomes. This approach has been adopted in order to ensure that the uniform collection of data allows the evaluation of the project objectives, as well as to meet the evaluation objectives.

Moreover, there is the aspect of evaluating the value of the results, as they are appreciated by the workers and the decision makers, coupled with the sense of the overall impact of SatisFactory. For this part, we make use of Questionnaires which are collective and associated to specific BSC, ET and ES and exploitable products. Two forms of them have been developed and revisited and they are used for the evaluation of the SatisFactory framework; the one is dedicated to the workers at the shop floor and the other to the decision makers involved in the respective procedure.

For assessing the overall impact of the SatisFactory framework in a more generic way, an Impact Check List has been produced and will be used for both levels of involvement (workers and decision makers).

The dedicated instruments developed are presented in Annexes I-IV. In Annex I, a set of standard questionnaires is provided, as well as the SatisFactory hybrid questionnaires, dedicated to the assessment of the evaluation tests by the workers. The same goes for Annex II, where a first generic approach is presented, followed by the dedicated SatisFactory questionnaires for the decision makers. Moreover, in Annex III the two Impact Check List are presented (one for the workers and one for the decision makers and other stakeholders), which will be used in all shop floors and it is of more importance during the second data collection, towards the completion of the second iteration of implementations. Finally, in Annex IV the exact Evaluation Tests are analysed. The Questionnaires and the Impact Check Lists can be also made available in other languages (for the scope of SatisFactory in Greek and Italian), if it is desired by the end users, to facilitate their usage at the pilot sites.

5. EVALUATION RESULTS AT CERTH/CPERI

An overview of the Evaluation Framework of SatisFactory that has been used at CERTH/CPERI is useful at this point. It is comprised by five Evaluation Scenarios and there are different questionnaires for the Workers and the Decision Makers.

In each questionnaire, there are two sections; the first being the general evaluation questions (SUS questionnaire) and the second being the SatisFactory specific evaluation questions (according to the five (5) criteria: Usability, Knowledge Integration, Working Experience, User Acceptance and Overall Impact).

People responding to the questionnaires may choose from five (5) available responses (Strongly Agree, Agree, Neither agree nor disagree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). For the general evaluation the first two options that convey a positive opinion have been grouped and the last two options that convey a negative opinion have been also grouped.

It is noted that the data collection includes also a Q&A/Comments section where the evaluators have the opportunity to share their remarks with the consortium. This procedure leads to improvements in the development process of the tools.

As discussed in Chapter 4, there were 2 data collection periods. Therefore, the results from the 2 different periods are shown, as well as a comparison among them. Moreover, the raw data from the data collection can be found in Annex V.

5.1 EVALUATION SCENARIO 1 RESULTS

It is reminded that the Evaluation Scenario 1 (Supporting Assembly Operations), is comprised by two scenarios (ES1.1: Automated support for assembly operations and ES1.2 AR supported assembly operations). The data collection is done using two questionnaires (ET1 Automated Support for Assembly Operations and ET2 AR Supported Assembly Operations).

The results from the general evaluation are shown for the first and second data collections in sections 5.1.1.1 and 5.1.1.2 respectively. Their comparison is shown in section 5.1.1.3.

5.1.1 ES1 Workers' Results

It is noted that during the 1st Data Collection period 4 workers responded to ET1.1 and 3 workers responded to ET1.2, while in the 2nd Data Collection period 8 workers responded to ET1.1 and 7 workers responded to ET1.2. Care has been taken, in order to have as representative as possible specimen, considering factors like the experience level, the years in current position and the age group. Since the overall sample is small, it was decided to present the profile of the responders collectively, considering both data collection periods.

Figure 10 Experience level, ES1-W, CERTH/CPERI

The level of experience of the responders is mainly intermediate and/or experienced, however the sample includes also workers who are novice and/or trainees. It is noted that the specimen is representative of the workforce of the personnel of CERTH/CPERI that is involved in the use of tools related to the Evaluation Scenario 1.

Figure 11 Years of employment, ES1-W, CERTH/CPERI

As shown above, half of the workers have 6-10 years of experience in the position they are in and half of them have 0-5. There are no workers among the ones involved in ES1 at CERTH/CPERI with more than 10 years of experienced in the position they are found at the moment.

Figure 12 Worker age, ES1-W, CETH/CPERI

Regarding the age groups, CETH/CPERI workers involved in ES1 are less than 39 years old, the majority of them being in the age group 30-39 years old. The distribution is representative of the working environment at the Industrial Lab.

5.1.1.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 13 General Evaluation of ES1-W, 1st DC, CETH/CPERI

As it is shown above, more than half of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 68% were either positive or neutral. The outcome of the selected feedback is visible in the second round of the evaluation.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 14 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, more than 60% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Usability and Knowledge Integration criteria of SatisFactory, while this percentage exceeded 88% for the Working Experience, User Acceptance and Overall Impact criteria. Remaining feedback was mostly neutral, with negative remarks only for the Usability (~ 17%) and Overall Impact (~ 5%) criteria.

5.1.1.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 15 General Evaluation of ES1-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, more than 70% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 82% were either positive or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 16 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, more than 70% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Satisfactory tools, while about 82% were either positive or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

5.1.1.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 17 General Evaluation of ES1-W, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, there is a significant improvement on the perception of the end users for ES1. While the positive feedback increased (by ~ 18%), the negative feedback decreased (by ~ 15%), while the neutral responses were kept at about the same level (~ 13%).

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 18 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more sceptical, especially to the aspects related to the knowledge integration criterion. This is due because of the personnel involved in the second round of data collection, along with their increased expectations after several months of developments.

Figure 19 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 20 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.1.2 ES1 Decision Makers' Results

During the 1st Data Collection period 2 decision makers responded to ET1.1 and no feedback was collected for ET2.2. This is due to the degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot, which were not mature enough for decision makers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection. Hence, in the 1st round, responses were collected only for ET1.2 and not ET2.2.

On the other hand, in the 2nd Data Collection period 3 decision makers responded to ET1.1 and 2 to ET1.2. Care has been taken, in order to have an as representative as possible specimen, considering factors like the experience level, the years in current position and the age group. Since the overall sample is small, it was decided to present the profile of the responders collectively, considering both data collection periods.

It is noted here that for the **experience level** was in all cases “Experienced” and that all decision makers involved belong to the **age group** “30-39”. The only differentiating factor is the years of employment, as shown in the next figure.

Figure 21 Years of employment, ES1-DM, CERTH/CPERI

5.1.2.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 22 General Evaluation of ES1-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

Almost half of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while 80% were either positive or neutral.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 23 Specific Evaluation of ES1-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, in most cases, responses were positive or neutral. Little negative feedback was collected. It should be kept in mind at all times that the sample is small, before drawing conclusions. Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact of SatisFactory criteria were the ones where decision makers provided negative responses.

5.1.2.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 24 General Evaluation of ES1-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, 55% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 85% were either positive or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 25 Specific Evaluation of ES1-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In most cases, responses were positive or neutral. Little negative feedback was collected. It should be kept in mind at all times that the sample is small, before drawing conclusions. Knowledge Integration and User Acceptance of SatisFactory criteria were the ones where decision makers were most sceptical.

5.1.2.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 26 General Evaluation of ES1-DM, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

There is a slight improvement on the perception of decision for ES1. The positive feedback increased (by 10%), the negative feedback decreased (by ~ 5%), while the neutral responses were kept at about the same level (~ 33%).

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 27 Specific Evaluation of ES1-DM, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more sceptical, especially to the aspects related to the knowledge integration and overall impact criteria. This is due because of the personnel involved in the second round of data collection, along with their increased expectations after several months of developments. It is also reminded that input for ET2.2 was not collected in the first round of data collection.

Figure 28 Specific Evaluation of ES1-DM, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 29 Specific Evaluation of ES1-DM, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.2 EVALUATION SCENARIO 2 RESULTS

The Evaluation Scenario 2 (Offering Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing Services) is comprised of two scenarios (ES2.1 Corrective Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing and ES2.2 Preventive Maintenance, Re-adaptation & HR Workload Balancing). The data collection is done using two questionnaires (ET3 Corrective Maintenance, Re-Adaptation & HR Workload Balancing and ET4 Preventive Maintenance, Re-Adaptation & HR Workload Balancing).

The results from the general evaluation are shown for the first and second data collections in sections 5.2.1.1 and 5.2.1.2 respectively for the Workers, then, sections 5.2.2.1 and 5.2.2.2 respectively for the Decision Makers. Their comparison is consecutively shown in section 5.2.1.3 (Workers) and Section 5.2.2.3 (Decision Makers).

5.2.1 ES2 Workers' Results

During the 1st Data Collection period 5 workers responded to ET3.1 and ET4.2, while in the 2nd Data Collection period 6 workers responded to ET3.1 and 7 workers responded to ET4.1. As a result, 23 questionnaires have been filled in for the ES2. Care has been taken, in order to have an as representative as possible specimen, considering factors like the experience level, the years in current position and the age group. Since the overall sample is small, it was decided to present the profile of the responders collectively, considering both data collection periods.

Figure 30 Experience level, ES2 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

The level of experience of the responders is mainly experienced (almost 61%), however the sample includes also workers who are novice and intermediate.

Figure 31 Years of employment, ES2 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

As shown above, almost 60% of the workers have more than 6 years of experience in the position they are in, the remaining 40% has between 0 and 5 years of experience.

Figure 32 Worker age, ES2 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

Regarding the age groups, CERTH/CPERI workers involved in ES2 are less than 39 years old, the majority of them being in the age group 30-39 years old. The distribution is representative of the working environment at the Industrial Lab.

5.2.1.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 33 General Evaluation of ES2-W, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

More than half of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 74% were either positive or neutral. The selected feedback is used to boost improvements.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 34 Specific Evaluation of ES2-W, 1st Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, 80% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Usability criterion, around 60% for the Working Experience and User Acceptance criteria and less than 40% for the Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact criteria of SatisFactory. It should be noted that negative feedback did not exceed 20% for any of the criteria.

5.2.1.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 35 General Evaluation of ES2-W, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, more than 80% of the responses on the positive side for the SatisFactory tools, while more than 97% were either positive or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 36 Specific Evaluation of ES2-W, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, more than 60% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Usability, Working Experience and User Acceptance criteria and around 40% for the Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact criteria of SatisFactory. It should be noted that negative feedback did not exceed about 20% for any of the criteria.

5.2.1.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 37 General Evaluation of ES2-W, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, there is a significant improvement on the satisfaction of the end users with ES2. While the positive feedback increased (by ~ 34%), the negative feedback decreased (by ~ 23%), while the neutral responses were decreased to almost half.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 38 Specific Evaluation of ES2-W, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling is that in the second data collection, people were convinced a bit more of the value of the SatisFactory tools, in comparison with the first phase of feedback with respect to ES2. They are more reserved in relation with the knowledge integration and overall impact criteria. The factor of resistance to change should be considered here, together with the reluctance of knowledge sharing to the extent that a worker may fear of becoming easily replaceable.

Figure 39 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 40 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.2.2 ES2 Decision Makers' Results

During the 1st Data Collection period 2 decision makers responded to ET3.1 and ET4.2, while in the 2nd Data Collection period 2 decision makers responded to ET3.1 and 1 responded to ET4.1. Taking into consideration the sample size, the profile of the responders is presented collectively, considering both data collection periods.

Figure 41 Experience level, ES2 Decision Maker, CERTH/CPERI

The level of experience of the responders is mainly experienced (about 70%), however the sample includes also decision makers with intermediate level of experience.

Figure 42 Years of employment, ES2 Decision Maker, CERTH/CPERI

Almost 70% of the decision makers have more than 6 years of experience in the position they are in, the remaining 30% has between 3 and 5 years of experience.

Figure 43 Worker age, ES2 Decision Maker, CERTH/CPERI

Regarding the age groups, CERTH/CPERI decision makers involved in ES2 are less than 39 years old, the majority of them being in the age group 30-39 years old.

5.2.2.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 44 General Evaluation of ES2-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

The 60% of gathered responses evaluated the SatisFactory tools related to ES2 in a positive way, while about 74% were either positive or neutral. The selected feedback is shared with the technology providing partners.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 45 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, 1st Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

For this case, User Acceptance and Overall Impact criteria gained the most positive feedback, while for the Usability, Working Experience and Knowledge Integration criteria won over half of the responders. Decision makers were more restrained in their opinion about the Knowledge Integration criterion. Again, the small sample size should be kept in mind.

5.2.2.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 46 General Evaluation of ES2-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

More than 65% of gathered responses evaluated the SatisFactory tools related to ES2 in a positive way, while about 82% were either positive or neutral. The comparison follows in the next section.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 47 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

In the second round of data collection, User Acceptance and Working Experience gained the most positive feedback, while the Usability and Overall Impact criteria won over about 60% of the responders. Decision Makers were sceptical about the Knowledge Integration aspect and there was also some restriction on the effect and Overall Impact of SatisFactory.

5.2.2.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 48 General Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

There is a slight improvement on the perception of decision for ES1. The positive feedback increased (by about 7%), the negative feedback increased (by ~ 10%), while the neutral responses decreased (~ 15%).

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 49 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more convinced, especially to the aspects related to the Usability, Working Experience and User Acceptance criteria. The effect that the Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact had on the responders was less prominent.

Figure 50 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 51 Specific Evaluation of ES2-DM, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.3 EVALUATION SCENARIO 3 RESULTS

It is reminded that the Evaluation Scenario 3 (Supporting Incident Detection & Recognition Operations), is comprised by two scenarios (ES3.1: Supporting recognition of incidents in equipment/operations and ES3.2 Recognizing Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor). The data collection is done using two questionnaires (ET6 Recognition of incidents in equipment/operations and ET7 Recognition of incidents with humans on the shop-floor).

Analysis for input of workers' is presented in section 5.3.1. Furthermore, detail results from both 1st and 2nd Data Collection are provided for decision makers in the section 5.3.2.

5.3.1 ES3 Workers' Results

During the 1st Data Collection period no workers responded to ET6.1. This was due to the status of ES3.1, as at that point it was applicable to SUNLIGHT, but not at CERTH/CPERI. Since then, ES3.1 has been modified and it is applicable to CERTH/CPERI. Hence, in the 2nd Data Collection, 5 workers provided their answers for ET6.1. For ET7.1, 5 workers responded to both Data Collections. The profile of the responders collectively, considering both data collection periods.

Figure 52 Experience level, ES3 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

Experienced personnel covered almost half of the sample, while the other half of the responders were either novice or intermediate.

Figure 53 Years of employment, ES3 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

Following the segmentation of the experience level, almost half had 6-10 years of experience, while the other half had less years of employment in the specific position.

Figure 54 Worker age, ES3 Workers, CERTH/CPERI

All workers were under 39 years old, with half of them being under 29 years old.

5.3.1.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 55 General Evaluation of ES3-W, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

As presented, 40% of the gathered responses provided a positive or neutral feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 25% were unconvinced. The outcome of the selected feedback is visible in the second round of the evaluation.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 56 Specific Evaluation of ES3-W, 1st Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, more than 60% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Usability and Working Experience criteria of SatisFactory. However, approximately the same percentage was reported neutral for the Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact. The only concern and remaining high negative remark and feedback were for Working Experience (~ 40%).

5.3.1.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 57 General Evaluation of ES3-W, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, more than 90% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 5% were either negative or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 58 Specific Evaluation of ES3-W, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection, more than 80% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while less than 20% were either negative or neutral. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

5.3.1.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 59 General Evaluation of ES3-W, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, there is a significant improvement on the perception of the end users for ES3. While the positive feedback increased (by ~ 10%), the negative feedback decreased (by ~ 12%), while the neutral responses were kept at about the same level (~ 17%).

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 60 Specific Evaluation of ES3-W, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more sceptical, especially to the aspects related to the knowledge integration criterion. This is due because of the personnel involved in the second round of data collection, along with their increased expectations after several months of developments.

Figure 61 Specific Evaluation of ES3-W, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 62 Specific Evaluation of ES3-W, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.3.2 ES3 Decision Makers' Results

During the 1st Data Collection period there were no decision makers responded to ET6.2 while 2 responses were collected for ET7.2. In the 2nd Data Collection period 2 decision makers responded to both these questionnaires. Taking into consideration the sample size, the profile of the responders is presented collectively, considering both data collection periods.

It is noted here that for the **experience level** was in all cases “Experienced” and that all decision makers involved have 10 and more years of experience and they belong to the **age group** “30-39”.

5.3.2.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 63 General Evaluation of ES3-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

Almost half of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools related to ES3, while less than 20% were either positive or neutral.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 64 Specific Evaluation of ES3-DM, 1st Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

This graph in most cases present positive or neutral responses. There was no negative feedback collected. It should be kept in mind at all times that the sample is small, before drawing conclusions. Note has to be made that there were no positive neither negative answers provided for Working Experience of SatisFactory criteria.

5.3.2.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 65 General Evaluation of ES3-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In the second data collection almost 80% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Satisfactory tools while about 20% were neutral and less than 3% was negative. This is a considerable improvement. The comparison follows in the next section.

Satisfactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 66 Specific Evaluation of ES3-DM, 2nd Data Collection, CERTH/CPERI

In most cases, responses were positive. Little neutral feedback was collected and no negative answers were provided.

5.3.2.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 67 General Evaluation of ES3-DM, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

There is a slight improvement on the perception of decision for ES3. The positive feedback increased (by ~ 12%), the negative feedback decreased (by ~ 12%), while the neutral responses were kept at the same level.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 68 Specific Evaluation of ES3-DM, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more positive, especially to the aspects related to the usability, users expectance and overall impact criteria. It has to be noted that there were no negative answers.

Figure 69 Specific Evaluation of ES3-DM, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 70 Specific Evaluation of ES3-DM, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.4 EVALUATION SCENARIO 4 RESULTS

Evaluation Scenario 4 (Offering “On-the-Job” Training Services) consists of three scenarios (ES4.1 Training environment set-up, ES4.2 Training support – Execution and ES4.3 Training support – Data Analysis). The data collection obtained within this scenario was based on one questionnaire, named On-the-job training in assembly operations (ET8.1 for worker and ET8.2 for decision maker). It has to be noted that during the 1st Data Collection period there were no responses collected from workers. However, in the 2nd Data Collection period 8 workers responded to the ET8.1 questionnaire and these results are presented in the section 5.4.1. Furthermore, sub-sections 5.4.2.1 and 5.4.2.2 present respectively and in details both results from 2 decision makers responses for 1st Data Collection period and 1 decision maker answers for 2nd Data Collection period.

5.4.1 ES4 Workers’ Results

It is noted that during the 1st Data Collection period there were no workers responses to ET8.1 while in the 2nd Data Collection period 8 workers responded to this questionnaire. The workers responses are summarised in pie charts presenting their experience level, years in current position and age group within CERTH/CPERI that are involved in the evaluation scenario 4. Furthermore, Supporting Assembly Operations of General and Specific Evaluation comparisons are presented further below.

Figure 71 Experience level, ES4-W, CERTH/CPERI

As presented directly above, the level of experience of the responders is mainly experienced. The sample includes also workers who are intermediate and/or trainees.

Figure 72 Years of employment, ES4-W, CERTH/CPERI

As shown above, more than 60% of workers have 6-10 years of experience in the position they are in and one quartile of all workers have 0-5. There are also workers with more than 10 years of experienced involved in this evaluation scenario ES4 in the position they are found at the moment.

Figure 73 Worker age, ES1-W, CERTH/CPERI

Regarding the age groups, CERTH/CPERI workers involved in ES4 are less than 39 years old, the majority of them being in the age group 30-39 years old. The distribution is representative of the working environment for this end user.

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 74 General Evaluation of ES1-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, there are no negative responses provided and less than 4% of answers are sceptic while more than 95% are with positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools. The outcome of the selected feedback is visible in the second round of the evaluation.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 75 Specific Evaluation of ES1-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

As presented above, all workers have responded positive for Usability while there are no neutral not negative answers. Approximately 75% and more, of responses were positive for User Acceptance and Overall impact. Remaining feedback was mostly neutral, with minor negative remarks for Knowledge Integration (~ 6%) and Working Experience (~ 3%).

5.4.2 ES4 Decision Makers' Results

During the 1st round of Data Collection period, 2 decision makers responded to ET8.1 while in the 2nd Data Collection period 1 decision maker responded to this questionnaire. Since the overall specimen is small, it was decided to present the profile of the responders collectively, considering both data collection periods.

It is noted here that for the **experience level** was in all cases “Experienced” and that all decision makers involved have more than 10 years of experience. The only differentiating factor is belong to the **age group** “30-39 as shown in the next figure.

Figure 76 Worker age, ES4-DM, CERTH/CPERI

5.4.2.1 1st Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 77 General Evaluation of ES4-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

Almost 40% of gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while 60% were either positive or neutral.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 78 Specific Evaluation of ES4-DM, 1st DC, CERTH/CPERI

As presented, in most cases, responses were positive, specifically Working Experience, User Acceptance and Overall Impact have 100%. Minor dubious were provided for Knowledge Integration while Usability obtained 25% of negative feedback.

5.4.2.2 2nd Data Collection

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 79 General Evaluation of ES4-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

Around 80% of gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while 10% were either positive or neutral.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 80 Specific Evaluation of ES4-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In most cases, responses were positive. There are no neutral answers, however around 50% responses from decision makers regarding Knowledge Integration and Working Experience were most sceptical.

5.4.2.3 Comparison

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 81 General Evaluation of ES4-DM, Comparison, CERTH/CPERI

It is noted that an increase of about 10% of the positive feedback of decision makers is observed for ES4, which corresponds approximately to the elimination of the negative feedback decreased in the 2nd Data Collection.

Satisfactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 82 Specific Evaluation of ES4-DM, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets is that for the specific evaluation, in the second data collection, people were more positive, especially to the aspects related to the Usability.

Figure 83 Specific Evaluation of ES4-DM, Comparison, Working Experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 84 Specific Evaluation of ES4-DM, Comparison, Overall Impact, CERTH/CPERI

5.5 EVALUATION SCENARIO 5 RESULTS

Evaluation Scenario 5 (Gamification and Collaboration Tools Usage) consists of two scenarios (ES5.1: Gamification Tools Usage and ES5.2: Collaboration Tools Usage). The data collection obtained within this scenario was based on two questionnaires, Gamification in shop floor working environment and Collaboration in shop floor working environment, for workers (ET9.1 and ET5.1) and for decision makers (ET9.2 and ET 5.2). It has to be noted that during the 1st Data Collection period there were no worker nor decision maker responses collected for ET9.1 nor ET5.1. However, in the 2nd Data Collection period 5 workers and 2 decision makers responded to these two questionnaires. Therefore, these 2nd Data Collection Results both for workers and decision makers are presented in sections 5.5.1 and 5.5.2 respectively.

5.5.1 ES5 Workers' Results

It is noted that during the 1st Data Collection period there were no workers responded to ET9.1 nor ET5.1. However, in the 2nd Data Collection period 5 workers responded to these two questionnaires. The sample, although small, is as representative as possible and the factors of the experience level, the years in current position and the age group have been taken into account.

Figure 85 Experience level, ES5-W, CERTH/CPERI

The level of experience of the responders is mainly novice and/or experienced. There are no trainee, however the sample includes also workers who are intermediate. It is noted that the specimen is representative of the workforce of the personnel of CERTH/CPERI that is involved in the use of tools related to the Evaluation Scenario 5 and 2nd Data Collection period only.

Figure 86 Years of employment, ES5-W, CERTH/CPERI

Even though, there are no workers with more than 10 years of experienced among the ones involved in ES5, 40 % of the workers have 6-10 years of experience and more than half of the workers have 0-5 in the position they are found at the moment at CERTH/ CPERI.

Figure 87 Worker age, ES5-W, CERTH/CPERI.

The majority of CERTH/CPERI workers involved in ES5 are mostly below 29 years old. Furthermore, working environment at the Industrial Lab consists of 40% of entire personnel within the age range of 30-39 years old.

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 88 General Evaluation of ES5-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

As it is shown above, more than 80% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while 20% were either neutral or negative. The outcome of the selected feedback is visible in the second round of the evaluation.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 89 Specific Evaluation of ES5-W, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

It is observed that more than 50% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the Usability and Knowledge Integration criteria of SatisFactory, while this percentage exceeded 75% for the Working Experience, User Acceptance and Overall Impact criteria. Remaining feedback was mostly neutral, with negative remarks only for the Usability (~ 8%), User Acceptance (~10%) and Overall Impact (~ 5%) criteria.

5.5.2 ES5 Decision Makers' Results

It has to be noted that during the 1st Data Collection period there were no decision makers' responses collected for ET9.1 nor for E5.1, as the level of implementations and tests was not mature enough. However, in the 2nd Data Collection period 2 decision makers responded to these two questionnaires. The experience level was declared as case "Experienced" and that both involved decision makers belong to the age group "30-39" with more than 10 years of employment.

General Evaluation (SUS Questionnaire)

Figure 90 General Evaluation of ES5-DM, 2nd DC, CERTH/CPERI

In the second and only data collection, 85% of the gathered responses provided a positive feedback for the SatisFactory tools, while about 15% were neutral. There were no negative responses.

SatisFactory Specific Evaluation

Figure 91 Specific Evaluation of ES5-DM, 2nd DC, CETH/CPERI

In most cases, responses were very positive or neutral. There was no negative feedback collected. It should be kept in mind at all times that the sample is small, before drawing conclusions. Usability, Knowledge Integration and Overall Impact of SatisFactory criteria were the ones where decision makers were most sceptical.

5.6 IMPACT CHECK LIST RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

It should be mentioned that 16 workers have provided several answers for various questions categorised in 5 criteria: Usability, Knowledge Integration, Perception of working experience, User Acceptance and Impact of SatisFactory. Each criterion consists of 3 questions where workers were responding positive, negative or neutral. The list of this questions and corresponding criteria are presented at Annex VI. The responses have been provided for 1st and 2nd data collection and they are presented in sections 5.6.1.1 and 5.6.1.2, respectively.

5.6.1 Workers' Results

Figure 92 Years of employment, IC-W, CERTH/CPERI

Even though, there are no workers with more than 10 years of experienced among the ones involved in this analyses, more than 60% of the workers have 6-10 years of experience and more than 37% of the workers have 0-5 in the position they are found at the moment at CERTH/ CPERI.

Figure 93 Experience level, IC-W, CERTH/CPERI

The level of experience of the responders is mainly intermediate and/or experienced. There are no trainee, however the sample includes also workers who are novice.

Figure 94 Worker age, IC-W, CERTH/CPERI.

The majority of CERTH/CPERI workers involved in IC analysis are mostly within the age range of 30-39 years old. Furthermore, working environment at the Industrial Lab consists as well as of less than 40% of personnel below 29 years old.

5.6.1.1 1st Data Collection

Figure 95 Impact check analysis, 1st DC, 5 criteria, CERTH/CPERI

During the 1st data collection, it is noted that workers have been very satisfied with the usability, user acceptance and impact of SaticFactory. (> 75%, in essence >80%). Negative answers were not many and only the case of knowledge integration stands out, where negative feedback was a bit of over 15%. Moreover, the perception of the working experience draws the attention, as 30% of workers were reluctant to associate the SaticFactory tools with it.

5.6.1.2 2nd Data Collection

Figure 96 Specific Impact check analysis, 2nd DC, 5 criteria, CERTH/CPERI

During the 2nd data collection, it is notice that workers have been very satisfied with the usability, knowledge integration and user acceptance. (> 75%). There are not many negative and/or neutral answers. What needs to be mentioned here is that the perception of working experience and the overall impact of SatisFactory were the two (2) criteria for which positive feedback was less than 75%.

5.6.1.3 Comparison

Figure 97 Evaluation of IC-W, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

The overall feeling one gets for the usability, is that in the second data collection, people were more convinced on the usability of the SatisFactory tools. Furthermore, there was a minor improvement during the 2nd DC for the knowledge integration criterion, which received ~ 5 % less negative responses than in the 1st DC. The level of user acceptance did not change. In what concerns the perception of the working experience, there was an increase of the positive feedback. The small increase of the negative feedback is attributed to certain issues that tools were facing at the point of the evaluation (instabilities, inconsistencies, etc.). The same goes for the impact of SatisFactory as a whole. It is worth mentioning that tools were still under development in M25, where the 2nd DV occurred at CERTH/CPERI and that the final versions were delivered in M30, taking into considerations remarks from the users of the Industrial Lab.

Figure 98 Evaluation of IC-W, Comparison, Perception of working experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 99 Evaluation of IM-W, Impact of SatisFactory, CERTH/CPERI

5.6.2 Decision Makers' Results

It has to be noted that all 5 decision makers have provided their answers based on the questions listed in annex VII. All of them have more than 10 years of experience and they are in the range age 30-39 years old.

5.6.2.1 1st Data Collection

Figure 100 Impact check analysis, 1st DC, 5 criteria, CERTH/CPERI

During the 1st data collection, decision makers' answers showed that they had a positive feeling for the knowledge of integration, user acceptance and overall impact of SatisFactory, (>75%). They had no negative perception regarding the usability of the tools. As far as the perception of working experience is concerned, it is noted that questions are mostly related to the aspects of training and collaboration, which were not mature enough at the point of the 1st DC. Hence, decision makers had not yet experienced much the use of these tools. In turn, this led to the perception that these aspects are mostly not applicable to the CERTH/CPERI shop floor.

5.6.2.2 2nd Data Collection

Figure 101 Impact check analysis, 2nd DC, 5 criteria, CERTH/CPERI

During the 1st data collection, decision makers' answers showed that they had a positive feeling for four (4) out of the five (5) SatisFactory criteria, (>75%). No change was reported on the impact they foresee regarding the usability.

5.6.2.3 Comparison

Figure 102 Evaluation of IC-DM, Comparison, Usability and Knowledge Integration, CERTH/CPERI

From the 1st to the 2nd DC, minor improvement on the expected impact was observed, in what concerns the knowledge integration and the user acceptance criteria. No change was noted neither for the usability nor for the overall impact. However, decision makers were not as convinced about the impact that the SatisFactory tools may have on the usability. This is due to certain issues that the associated tools were still facing at the time of the evaluation, mainly concerning instability and connectivity with other SatisFactory tools and the existing infrastructure. Moreover, significant increase was monitored for the expected impact on the knowledge integration from the decision makers of the Industrial Lab.

Figure 103 Evaluation of IC-DM, Comparison, Perception of working experience and User Acceptance, CERTH/CPERI

Figure 104 Evaluation of IM-DM, Impact of SatisFactory, CERTH/CPERI

5.7 OVERALL RESULTS ASSESSMENT

The evaluation process aims to offer benefits both to the technology providing partners and the end users. The technology providing partners get feedback for the components they develop and they get a chance to improve performance and characteristics, fix problems, improve usability etc. before putting them to more market-ready form.

In order to be able to benefit from the selected process of the evaluation three (3) levels of conclusions can be drawn and combined: i) based on the SUS, ii) based on the SatisFactory evaluation criteria, iii) based on the exploitable products.

5.7.1 Conclusions based on SUS

As it has been discussed in previous sections, SatisFactory has a user-centric character, hence a part of the evaluation tools have been designed following a human-centric evaluation methodology. The System Usability Scale (SUS) has been selected because it provides a quick and reliable tool for measuring the usability. As presented also in Annexes I and II, it consists of a 10 questions with five response options; from “Strongly agree” to “Strongly disagree”. This method (Brooke 1986) has been chosen because it can be applied for the evaluation of a variety of products and services, such as hardware, software, mobile applications etc. and because it can be used on small sample sizes with reliable results.

The first part of the prepared questionnaires is the 10 questions of the SUS. This part leads to a number which represents the overall usability of the system being studied for each ET. To calculate the SUS score, each response gets a score from 0 to 4. For items 1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 the score contribution is the scale position minus 1. For items 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10, the contribution is 5 minus the scale position. The sum is calculated and it is multiplied by 2.5 to obtain the overall value of SU. It is noted that SUS scores range from 0 to 100.

However, the calculation of the SUS score is not helpful by itself, it needs interpretation. Bangor et al. (Bangor 2009) provided an extensive study, in an effort to determine what individual SUS scores mean. This is visualised in the next figure. It is deduced that it is desired to have SUS scores that are above 50.

Figure 105 A comparison of the adjective ratings, acceptability scores, and school grading scales, in relation to the average SUS score

The results from the data collections at CPERI are provided below. It should be noted that they were unexpected, as they led to the categorisation of SatisFactory components as poor.

Table 4 SUS scores at CERTH/CPERI

ES	ET	Who	1 st	2 nd	Modified 2 nd
1	1	W (1.1)	25	30	54
1	1	DM (1.2)	35	33	59
1	2	W (2.1)	20	30	54
1	2	DM (2.2)	-	43	77
2	3	W (3.1)	41	29	52
2	3	DM (3.2)	36	24	43
2	4	W (4.1)	28	23	41
2	4	DM (4.2)	29	43	77
3	6	W (6.1)	-	25	45
3	6	DM (6.2)	-	31	56
3	7	W (7.1)	40	29	52
3	7	DM (7.2)	33	29	52
4	8	W (8.1)	-	29	52
4	8	DM (8.2)	38	28	50
5	5	W (5.1)	-	30	54
5	5	DM (5.2)	-	39	70
5	9	W (9.1)	-	37	67
5	9	DM (9.2)	-	31	56

This result was not consistent with the verbal feedback from the participants. Thus, it was necessary to further investigate why people responded in the way they did. After talking to the involved personnel, two main points stood out:

1. CERTH/CPERI employees are accustomed to work in demanding environments with state-of-the-art tools, they work with high standards and they were reluctant to provide the answers “Strongly Agree” or “Strongly Disagree”.
2. CERTH/CPERI employees provided their responses considering a market-ready product, i.e. at TRL 9. However, according also to the Grant Agreement, the TRL of the final products is expected at a range from 4 to 7. The mean expected TRL is 5, roughly 6 at the end of the project.

It is reminded that some tools were not ready to the extent that the evaluation was possible at the point of the 1st Data Collection. At the time of the 2nd Data Collection it was possible to evaluate all tools. At that point, the mean TRL 5 can be considered as 5. For this reason, it was decided to adjust the SUS scores with a multiplier of (*9/5), in order to tackle the distorted view, as the perception of the responders -according to the discussions with them- was that the tools were not poor, but good.

Consequently, the overall outcome for the evaluated SatisFactory components at CERTH/CPERI is that, in terms of **usability**, they are **good**.

5.7.2 Conclusions based on SatisFactory evaluation criteria

In order to draw conclusions from the responses on the SatisFactory specific questions (11 through 20), i.e. the second half of the questionnaires, it was decided to view them per criterion. For this scope, it was considered appropriate to take into account the positive feedback as the weighing factor and to consider that a score of 70% is translated to an acceptable outcome.

The results of the analysis described below is that the **evaluation process** was **successful** and it made it possible for technology providing partners to **understand the end users' point of view per criterion**. Moreover, it offered the chance for end users to detect issues of SatisFactory components that were conveyed to the responding technology providing partners and, in turn, **led to technical improvements** during the second iteration of the development of the tools.

It is reminded that for each Evaluation Scenario (ES), both the Worker (W) and the Decision Maker (DM) points of view have been considered.

5.7.2.1 Conclusions for Usability

It is reminded that as described in section 2.2.4, Usability is one of the most widely used tools for assessing the perceived usability of a product by a user. Since SatisFactory includes visualisation, incident management and decision support components, it is important to consider the appeal of the design, the suitability and the effect on the shop floor, the learnability and applicability.

Table 5 Positive feedback for the Usability Criterion at CERTH/CPERI

ES	Who	1 st	2 nd
1	W	66.67	87.05
1	DM	25	43.75
2	W	80	78.36
2	DM	50	41.67
3	W	73.33	86.67
3	DM	75	100
4	W	-	100
4	DM	25	100
5	W	-	64
5	DM	-	87.5

The overall feedback shows that the personnel were satisfied with the usability of the SatisFactroy tools. However, for ES1 and ES2, the decision makers were not convinced. For ES1, this is due to what DMs perceived as low implementation level at that time at CPERI, especially for the AR related functionalities. For ES2, the same goes for the functionalities related to the visualisation of the re-adaptation and HR scheduling. It should be noted that these remarks were conveyed to the respective technology providing partners and mitigation measures were taken in the M30 version of the components. Moreover, for ES5 the workers were more sceptical. The discussion showed that workers were not much into the suggestion platform, although they thought it is an interesting concept and that they did not feel more playful in their working environment due to the usage of the platform. The idea of “advertising campaigns” within the shop floor was put on the table, in order to motivate and engage more the users. Again, this was transferred to the technology providing partners.

5.7.2.2 Conclusions for Knowledge Integration

The assessment of Knowledge Integration relates to the performance of the semantic models, to the exploitation of the shop floor knowledge and exposure through the SatisFactory platform and to the different views of information depending on the organisational level and localisation of the end-users.

Table 6 Positive feedback for the Knowledge Integration Criterion at CERTH/CPERI

ES	Who	1 st	2 nd
1	W	62.5	39.75
1	DM	25	65
2	W	35	46.67
2	DM	50	33.33
3	W	30	100
3	DM	100	83.33
4	W	-	75
4	DM	75	50
5	W	-	50
5	DM	-	50

With the exception of the responses for ES3, there were concerns for the aspect of knowledge integration. The interviews with the responders showed that there were some technical difficulties with the timely presentation of appropriate information, as well as with the readability in some cases. Moreover, the users of the localisation manager had spotted some inconsistencies. Also, users did not feel as confident and motivated as they would like to be in what concerns the AR tools and the collaboration and gamification platform. It is noted that these remarks were shared with the technology providing partners, who in turned addressed these issues. Hence, the evaluation process is considered a success, as it led to the amelioration of the developed tools, with the consideration of the end users' point of view.

5.7.2.3 Conclusions for Perception of Working Experience

The evaluation of the Perception of Working Experience relates to the introduction of gamification and collaboration tools and the use of AR-based devices and tools. These are expected to modify the work environment and to have an impact on the perception of the working experience.

Table 7 Positive feedback for the Perception of Working Experience Criterion at CETH/CPERI

ES	Who	1 st	2 nd
1	W	91.67	85.57
1	DM	100	41.67
2	W	60	73.33
2	DM	50	83.33
3	W	60	86.67
3	DM	-	100
4	W	-	68.75
4	DM	100	50
5	W	-	70
5	DM	-	100

For the Perception of Working Experience criterion, some constraints are visible for ES1 and ES4 from the decision makers and for ES4 from the workers. In essence, there were concerns for ES1, rather than negative evaluation. They were a result of the expectations of the DMs for that point of the project and they were mostly related to the reuse of AR tools and the impact on ergonomics, safety and/or reduction of requests for help. In the case of ES4, while both workers and decision makers felt that the on-the-job-training platform is an improvement to the existing system and can lead to skills enrichment, they were not convinced that the SatisFactory tools are able to provide complete and reliable training. This oxymoron can be explained by the fact that CETH/CPERI personnel felt they did not receive enough training and that they did not “play” enough with the on-the-job training platform. This was brought to the attention of the technology providing partners and it was also partially addressed with the content of *D6.5 End-users VR-enabled training material and scenarios* in M30.

5.7.2.4 Conclusions for User Acceptance

The scope is to evaluate user acceptance as the willingness of the involved stakeholders to embrace and reuse the developed tools in their everyday activities also after the project’s lifetime.

Table 8 Positive feedback for the User Acceptance Criterion at CERTH/CPERI

ES	Who	1 st	2 nd
1	W	88.89	76.19
1	DM	50	62.5
2	W	56	65
2	DM	83.33	100
3	W	53.33	76.67
3	DM	75	87.5
4	W	-	87.5
4	DM	100	100
5	W	-	71.43
5	DM	-	100

In this context, concerns were expressed by the decision makers for ES1 and by workers for ES2. In the first case, half of the decision makers had a positive overall feedback for SatisFactory while the other half remained neutral. Taking into consideration the small sample of responses, this outcome is not alarming. Also, there was an interesting finding in relation to the AR tools. While decision makers had the feeling that the Standard Operating Procedures required in the pilot test are transformed into AR tools, they were sceptical in what concerns the successful access to data/information via the AR platform. This is again explained by the fact that CERTH/CPERI personnel felt they did not receive enough training and that they did not “play” enough with the on-the-job training platform. In the second case, workers did not feel more as member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication, due to SatisFactory. This is due to two main reasons; CERTH/CPERI personnel have already an increased sense of team spirit and –most importantly– the collaboration and gamification platforms had a different form at the time of the data collection, which was a bit confusing to the users.

The outcome of the procedure is regarded as a success. It gave the chance to technology providing partners relevant to the AR tools and the on-the-job training platform to seek more involvement of the personnel at the Industrial Pilots. Also, it led to the unification of the collaboration and gamification platforms with a more attractive and straightforward form.

5.7.2.5 Conclusions for Overall Impact

Table 9 Positive feedback for Overall Impact Criterion at CERTH/CPERI

ES	Who	1 st	2 nd
1	W	95	72.14
1	DM	66.67	81.25
2	W	24	34
2	DM	60	60
3	W	40	80
3	DM	75	93.75
4	W	-	75
4	DM	100	100
5	W	-	75
5	DM	-	71.43

Concerns related to the overall impact were expressed both by workers and decision makers. They both mentioned that the system fails frequently, which was conveyed to the technology providing partners and led to more stable solutions. There were also remarks from the workers about the aesthetic attractiveness and from decision makers about the incident management tools, which were again were transferred to the respective partners and the outcome is evident in the M30 version of the SatisFactory components.

5.7.3 Connection to exploitable products and results of data collection

The data collection and evaluation process offers the possibility to product developing partners and end users to interact. It is a two way process. End users fill questionnaires but also have a chance to communicate their experiences and concerns. The **evaluation process for exploitable products** is considered very helpful and valuable, since it gives the opportunity to understand the end users' point of view and their expectations. It also **helps** product developers to **morph** their **exploitation path** and modify the trajectory of the developments if necessary.

Along with the points discussed in the two previous sections, it is of interest to highlight the outcome from the evaluation per each identified exploitable result of the SatisFactory project at this stage.

Semantics and Context-aware knowledge shop floor analysis engine

The evaluation of this product is indirect, as it runs on the background and end users do not interact with it. However, responders are able to assess it, as they experience the results related to its functionality. Comments showed that end users consider that it is of critical importance for efficient human resource management, incident detection and incident

management. Remarks are tied mainly with the quality of the information and grouping made available. Hence, it is possible for the technology providing partners to make improvements and to consider the specific needs of individual shop floors, while keeping a standardised structure.

Real-time localization of workers, tools and machines

While the localisation tools are viewed as an attractive addition to the existing infrastructure that enables increased safety and monitoring, especially for restricted or dangerous areas, there were two main concerns for the localisation tools. The first addresses the technical aspect of the actual implementation. Instabilities and delays were spotted by the end users, which led to improvements of these features. The second relates to the way that these tools are presented to the personnel at the shop floor. It is of critical importance to convey to them that the solutions proposed by SatisFactory respect the privacy of the workers and that they are used to improve safety features, to reduce work related accidents and stress and to increase workers' satisfaction.

Dynamic Re-adaptation of Production Facilities

It was successfully communicated to the end users that the scope of this product is to facilitate the re-adaptation of production facilities by incorporating data for the status of the production processes. The remarks were mainly on some inconsistencies that technology developing partners were able to fix at a later version and on the attractiveness of the Human Machine Interface (HMI) which were also taken into account and tackled. In general it was viewed as an interesting product with the potential of being more useful for larger shop floors.

HR workload balancing toolkit (Incident management)

Responders were interested in the toolkit which offers the ability to manage effectively the human resources available on the shop floor level at all times. Personnel viewed this product as very useful for environments where high specification in skills is required to perform certain tasks or when production issues require for fast and efficient visualisation of the current situation and re-adaptation. The comments were mainly related to instabilities of the system and the actual implementation, in terms of pinpointing the suitable personnel. Moreover, there were remarks for the different views offered to the different levels of personnel. Again, technology providing partners were able to address these issues and to provide an improved version in M30.

Feedback Engine (incident detection)

SatisFactory offers the possibility to monitor the activities on the shop floor and to rise an alert at the high possibility of a risky condition (proactive incident) and for incidents after their occurrence (reactive) based on real-time data. Responders were pleased with the aspect of health and safety issues detection and avoidance. The overall feeling is that this tool will help form a safer environment. Based on the remarks, it was deducted that it is of high importance to convey to the end users that only privacy preserving sensors are used, in order to respect of the personnel's legal and ethical rights. Additionally, there were findings related to the

timely transfer of the alarm and the notification, which were improved by the responsible partners.

On-the-job training toolkit

The evaluation of this product is viewed by the personnel as the evaluation of the ability to conduct a more or less unsupervised on-the-job training using the AR platform for industrial environments. The overall feedback is positive but the main concerns expressed are relevant to the amount of work and complexity that is required to insert a new SOP in the toolkit. Hence, in terms of the exploitation path, it is made evident to the exploiting partners that it is critical to produce an approach/demo that visualises and convinces that this procedure is simple and easy enough. On the positive note, the interaction with HMD is considered a plus, as well as the level of ease of use of the visualisations. An interesting outcome is that decision makers consider that the ROI is satisfying.

Hardware HMI, HMD

Within SatisFactory, Glassup further extends the features of their glasses, taking into account both ergonomics and other critical factors for end-users final acceptance in industrial applications. The personnel is interested in the potential for a two-ways data transfer. The design and functionality implementation at the point of the evaluation was not to the level of the expectations of the responders, however they were interested in exploring the potential that this product offer for upscaling the working environment. Some concerns were related to the duration of usage. From the exploitation point of view, the feedback was very useful, in the sense that it gave the exploiting partners the point of view of the end users and that it made them focus to the promotion of certain functionality and usability characteristics.

Integrated shop floor DSS

The DSS may run on the background, but it is possible for responders to evaluate it, as there is a visualisation tool for both the decision makers and the workers that conveys the deducted information. The functionality that captures the most interest of the personnel is the ability to couple detected incidents with prescribed response strategies and to offer feedback to the shop floor in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations, including maintenance operations and schedules. Remarks of the decision makers are related to the ease of modification of the shop floor specific rules in the rule engine. The response of the developing providing partners, in terms of exploitation is to address this issue with more details assuring the involved personnel on the ease of use. Moreover, there are comments from the workers using the shop floor feedback engine application, mostly related to visualisation suggestions and sporadic fails of the system. This valuable information is translated into a more stable, user friendly update of the application.

Gamification/Collaboration platform for manufacturing enterprises

One of the main aspects and advantages of SatisFactory is the use of standard user-centred technology design methods in order to appropriately address the challenges of the shop floor environment. The personnel evaluating the gamification/collaboration platform understand that it offers an attractive collaboration and interaction environment with transparency, while

respecting the privacy of workers. Responders acknowledge the novel gamified environment and the potential to enhance the attractiveness of the working environment and collaboration. The key concern relates to the applicability at the specific shop floor, mainly because it is not clear how the motivation and employee engagement is going to be accomplished. Hence, technology providing partners are left with the challenge to convince on the applicability and adaptability of the platform at different shop floors. This is a valuable outcome that can further influence the design and exploitation process.

Middleware for Smart Factories

The assessment in this case is indirect, as the LinkSmart middleware runs on the background. It is perceived by the responders as the enabler of shop floor data aggregation, notification and control. Concerns are related to the stability of the system, the adjustability, the timely transfer of data and the suitability of the presented information. All the input has been put to good use by the technology providing partners, leading to a more stable version that enables improved usability and user experience.

Smart Sensor Network for Industrial Applications

The scope is to evaluate if and how the Smart Sensor Network (SSN) provides communication robustness in industrial environments by taking advantage of heterogeneous wireless technologies. The input shows that it is viewed as a progress that enables near-real-time knowledge transfer with the option for prompt reaction to potential communication interruptions. Concerns are expressed on whether and how it is possible to adjust and integrate to existing infrastructures or to migrate existing sensors in the SatisFactory SSN. This is transferred to the technology providing partners, in order to help them plan better the exploitation process and tools. Instabilities detected and reported have been taken into account to produce a more robust network.

CONCLUSIONS

The current deliverable aims at describing the evaluation framework and its realisation plan with the use of evaluation scenarios and provides the methodological framework for the assessment of the SatisFactory platform during the pilot realisation and therefore the guidelines for effective execution of the pilot scenarios. The evaluation objectives, along with the methodological framework served as the base for five Evaluation Scenarios which have been analysed along with the process for the system evaluation in terms of performance and user experience from the end user point of view. The steps that each assessment method follows and the measurement tools to be used in each case have been also defined in specific evaluation tests.

The criteria used for the evaluation framework were:

- Usability
- Knowledge integration
- Perception of working experience
- User acceptance
- Impact of SatisFactory

This document outlines the approach to the assessment and the associated tools which has been revisited in T5.2 iterations (e.g. definition of indicators (metrics), data collection tools, implementation of evaluation scenarios).

In order to perform the overall evaluation of SatisFactory, questionnaires have been prepared aiming at different target groups; workers and decision-makers, as well as an overall impact check list. These tools are to be used for 2 data collections at each shop floor, in different time periods for the 3 end users involved in the project. Prior to the data collections the Evaluation Workshops are organised, as well as the following Information Sessions. The experience gained from the application to the Industrial Lab is presented in the current and final version of D5.2 and it will serve as the basis for the evaluation at the industrial pilots, which will be presented in D5.5.

The methodology described in the M14 iteration was applied at the Industrial Lab pilot at CERTH/CPERI. It should be noted that the description of the Evaluation Scenarios, as well as the feedback forms and tools have been revisited in the second iteration of the deliverable. This was necessary, in order to take into consideration the technological advancement of the project's components. The results are shown in chapter 5 of the current version of the deliverable.

The feedback from the shop floors is iteratively assessed, in order to improve functionalities, features and to detect at an early stage of the strong and weak points, aiming always at increasing worker satisfaction, safety and well-being. It is of great importance, as it leads to product improvements before the implementation at the industrial pilots and it enables partners to adjust their exploitation approach.

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ANNEXE I: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR WORKERS

SYSTEM USABILITY SCALE

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1	2	3	4	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	1	2	3	4	5
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1	2	3	4	5
4. I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	1	2	3	4	5
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1	2	3	4	5
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	1	2	3	4	5
7. I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	1	2	3	4	5
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	1	2	3	4	5
9. I felt very confident using the system	1	2	3	4	5
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	1	2	3	4	5

ATTRAKDIFF

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

human	<input type="radio"/>	technical						
isolating	<input type="radio"/>	connective						
pleasant	<input type="radio"/>	unpleasant						
inventive	<input type="radio"/>	conventional						
simple	<input type="radio"/>	complicated						
professional	<input type="radio"/>	unprofessional						
ugly	<input type="radio"/>	attractive						
practical	<input type="radio"/>	impractical						
likeable	<input type="radio"/>	disagreeable						
cumbersome	<input type="radio"/>	straightforward						

1/3 cancel next

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

stylish	<input type="radio"/>	tacky						
predictable	<input type="radio"/>	unpredictable						
cheap	<input type="radio"/>	premium						
alienating	<input type="radio"/>	integrating						
brings me closer to people	<input type="radio"/>	separates me from people						
unpresentable	<input type="radio"/>	presentable						
rejecting	<input type="radio"/>	inviting						
unimaginative	<input type="radio"/>	creative						
good	<input type="radio"/>	bad						

2/3 cancel next

 ■ Greeting ■ How it works ■ **Your Evaluation** ■ Personal Data ■ Submit

Evaluation of the product SatisFactory

With the help of the word-pairs please enter what you consider the most appropriate description for **SatisFactory**. Please click on your choice in every line!

confusing	<input type="radio"/>	clearly structured						
repelling	<input type="radio"/>	appealing						
bold	<input type="radio"/>	cautious						
innovative	<input type="radio"/>	conservative						
dull	<input type="radio"/>	captivating						
undemanding	<input type="radio"/>	challenging						
motivating	<input type="radio"/>	discouraging						
novel	<input type="radio"/>	ordinary						
unruly	<input type="radio"/>	manageable						

3/3 cancel next

UEQ – USER EXPERIENCE QUESTIONNAIRE

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
annoying	<input type="radio"/>	enjoyable	1						
not understandable	<input type="radio"/>	understandable	2						
creative	<input type="radio"/>	dull	3						
easy to learn	<input type="radio"/>	difficult to learn	4						
valuable	<input type="radio"/>	inferior	5						
boring	<input type="radio"/>	exciting	6						
not interesting	<input type="radio"/>	interesting	7						
unpredictable	<input type="radio"/>	predictable	8						
fast	<input type="radio"/>	slow	9						
inventive	<input type="radio"/>	conventional	10						
obstructive	<input type="radio"/>	supportive	11						
good	<input type="radio"/>	bad	12						
complicated	<input type="radio"/>	easy	13						
unlikable	<input type="radio"/>	pleasing	14						
usual	<input type="radio"/>	leading edge	15						
unpleasant	<input type="radio"/>	pleasant	16						
secure	<input type="radio"/>	not secure	17						
motivating	<input type="radio"/>	demotivating	18						
meets expectations	<input type="radio"/>	does not meet expectations	19						
inefficient	<input type="radio"/>	efficient	20						
clear	<input type="radio"/>	confusing	21						
impractical	<input type="radio"/>	practical	22						
organized	<input type="radio"/>	cluttered	23						
attractive	<input type="radio"/>	unattractive	24						
friendly	<input type="radio"/>	unfriendly	25						
conservative	<input type="radio"/>	innovative	26						

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
16 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
17 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 WE3	I have used the AR tools					
16 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
17 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
18 UA3	I think that AR platform successfully provides access to data/information					
19 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
16 WE1	The SatisFactory platform demonstrates safety and ergonomomy procedures					
17 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
18 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
19 OI3	The system fails frequently					
20 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U9	The framework provides a variety of visualisations					
13 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
14 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
15 WE1	The SatisFactory platform demonstrates safety and ergonomony procedures					
16 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
17 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U2	I need less time to perform a single task					
13 U5	I have successfully used the suggestion platform and it is likely that I will reuse it					
14 U10	I feel more motivated and playful in my workplace due to the usage of the platform					
15 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
16 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
17 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
18 UA4	I submit more than 3 suggestions per year to the suggestion platform					
19 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
20 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET6.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 U8	SatisFactory provides straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 WE5	The SatisFactory tools enable continuous monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
14 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
15 KI6	The identification of patterns of workers' movement is successful					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
12 KI3	The average time for training procedures is reduced					
13 KI11	The AR tools of SatisFactory provide efficient information					
14 WE2	The on-the-job-training platform is an improvement to the existing system and the sessions are useful for knowledge and skills enrichment					
15 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 WE8	The SatisFactory tools are able to provide complete and reliable training					
18 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
19 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(WORKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U10	I feel more motivated and playful in my workplace due to the usage of the platform					
12 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
13 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
14 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
15 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
16 UA10	I think that gamification tools increase the attractiveness of the shop floors					
17 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

ANNEXE II: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DECISION MAKERS

- 1) How do you consider the time required for the development of a new application?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 2) How do you consider the time spent from departments not directly involved in the development and the setting up of an application?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 3) How do you consider the direct cost sustained for the acquiring of specific hardware devices for workers?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 4) How do you consider the indirect costs related to the creation and the taking care of an optimal working site, as required for the trial (installation of cameras and additional lighting point, toolset, RFID and antennas,..)?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 5) How do you consider the indirect cost related to the maintenance and the taking care of the wearable personal workers' devices (clean, protected, ..)?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 6) How do you consider the obtained percentage of reuse of the AR applications?
1 = totally acceptable
5 = totally unacceptable

- 7) How seems the Application integrated in the rest of the processes?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

8) How do you consider the adequateness of the software in order to preserve the privacy of workers?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

9) How do you consider the adequateness of the installed systems in order to preserve the safety of workers?

1 = totally acceptable

5 = totally unacceptable

10) As far as concerns with the objectives of reducing errors, what is the percentage of initial objectives reached with the trial?

A value ranging from 0% to 100%

11) As far as concerns with the objective of reducing the cost of maintenance, what is the percentage of initial objectives reached with the trial?

A value ranging from 0% to 100%

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
16 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
17 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
18 OI6	The failures of the system are critical					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 KI11	The AR tools of SatisFactory provide efficient information					
16 WE4	I am likely to reuse the AR tools					
17 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
18 UA3	I think that AR platform successfully provides access to data/information					
19 UA7	The Standard Operating Procedures required in the pilot test are transformed into AR tools					
20 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
13 U8	SatisFactory provides straightforward visualisations of the shop floor status					
14 U9	The framework provides a variety of visualisations					
15 KI5	The SatisFactory platform reinforces collaboration on the shop floor					
16 WE6	The use SatisFactory tools increases safety for workers at the shop floors					
17 WE9	The SatisFactory tools contribute to the reduction of work-related stress					
18 UA6	The use of SatisFactory contributes to reduction of process or machine downtime					
19 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
20 OI8	The SatisFactory tools are fit for the purpose they were developed					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
12 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
13 KI1	The SatisFactory tools provide appropriate data/information					
14 KI12	SatisFactory tools provide unreadable and incomprehensible data/information					
15 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
16 UA2	The lessons learned from the pilot trials are applicable to everyday activities					
17 UA9	SatisFactory reduces misinterpretations					
18 OI3	The system fails frequently					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI6	The failures of the system are critical					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U1	I complete tasks effectively and successfully using the SatisFactory platform					
12 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
13 U6	SatisFactory provides appropriate suggestions for re-adaptation and work assignment					
14 U7	SatisFactory helps identify areas for process improvement and/or process bottlenecks					
15 KI5	The SatisFactory platform reinforces collaboration on the shop floor					
16 KI8	Suggestions submitted to the SatisFactory platform are accepted					
17 WE7	The number of requests for help to other workers/experts is reduced					
18 UA5	I use the collaboration platform more than 3 times per year					
19 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET6.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS
(DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 WE5	The SatisFactory tools enable continuous monitoring of production parameters using thermal cameras					
15 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
16 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
17 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U4	The framework is able to successfully identify incidents at the shop floor					
13 KI2	The data/information are received on time via the SatisFactory platform					
14 KI6	The identification of patterns of workers' movement is successful					
15 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
16 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
17 OI1	SatisFactory platform handles incidents at the shop floors					
18 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
19 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS (DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 U3	SatisFactory contributes to the reduction of failures					
12 U11	SatisFactory facilitates task performance					
13 KI3	The average time for training procedures is reduced					
14 KI7	SatisFactory tools can locate the position of objects in the shop floor with high accuracy, thus reducing errors					
15 KI9	I think the necessary time for the preparation of training procedures is reduced using the SatisFactory tools					
16 KI10	SatisFactory tools helps reduce training costs					
17 WE2	The on-the-job-training platform is an improvement to the existing system and the sessions are useful for knowledge and skills enrichment					
18 WE8	The SatisFactory tools are able to provide complete and reliable training					
19 UA12	My overall feedback for SatisFactory is positive					
20 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					

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QUESTIONNAIRE ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT
(DECISION MAKERS)

Please rate from 1: Strongly agree to 5: Strongly disagree, for the given statements.

N.	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	I think that I would like to use this system frequently					
2	I found the system unnecessarily complex					
3	I thought the system was easy to use					
4	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system					
5	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated					
6	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system					
7	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly					
8	I found the system very cumbersome to use					
9	I felt very confident using the system					
10	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system					

N. (KPI)	Statement	Rate				
		1	2	3	4	5
11 KI4	I have submitted several suggestions using the SatisFactory suggestion platform					
12 UA1	I am motivated and engaged to use the SatisFactory framework					
13 UA8	SatisFactory improves the sense of team spirit					
14 UA10	I think that gamification tools increase the attractiveness of the shop floors					
15 UA11	SatisFactory helps me feel as a member of a community that uses novel ways for social interaction and communication					
16 OI2	The features and the functionality of SatisFactory tools are satisfying					
17 OI4	The cost for platform installation, operation and maintenance is small in compare with all the functionalities that the platform provides					
18 OI5	I think that the Return On Investment is good					
19 OI7	The SatisFactory tools are applicable at the shop floor					
20 OI9	The SatisFactory framework is aesthetically attractive					

ANNEXE III: IMPACT CHECK LIST

Checklist for Impact Analysis	
Overview	<p>Impact Analysis is being done because a change is occurring at the shop floor level in terms of work management and introduction of new devices.</p> <p>The checklist below can be used when evaluating the impact of SatisFactory in each Pilot Site.</p>
Evaluation Criteria	<p>The following criteria should be met (when applicable):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability • Knowledge integration • Perception of working experience • User acceptance • Impact of SatisFactory
End-Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worker • Decision maker
Exit Criteria	<p>The following criteria should be met after using this checklist.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Impact Analysis is complete and shows no undesired impacts are caused by the introduction of new tools • Evaluation plans have been updated to verify the evolution of the shop floor performances

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IMPACT CHECK LIST 1 (WORKERS)

PILOT SITE:					
#	Criteria	Yes	No	N/A	Remarks
Usability					
	<i>The SF platform provides appropriate visualisation and incident management tools.</i>				
	<i>The required information (resources, data and guidelines) is available in real-time.</i>				
	<i>The information provided through the SF platform is appropriate and easy to understand.</i>				
Knowledge Integration					
	<i>The provided training methods, content and materials improve the process of knowledge and skills enrichment required to perform tasks.</i>				
	<i>The SF platform promotes collaboration and knowledge sharing between the workers at the shop floor.</i>				
	<i>The shop floor knowledge is managed and presented through the SF platform in an attractive way.</i>				
Perception of working experience					
	<i>The use of AR tools in daily activities is attractive and improves the working experience on the shop-floor.</i>				
	<i>The SF on-the-job training system is innovative and the visualisations offered facilitate memorisation.</i>				
	<i>The introduced collaboration and gamification elements empower the team spirit.</i>				
User Acceptance					
	<i>The use of the SF tools helps performing daily operations more efficiently and with less mental effort.</i>				

	<i>The use of the new tools and technologies reduces fatigue and discomfort and improves the quality of work.</i>				
	<i>The introduction of the SF framework is well received and the users are confident to employ the proposed technologies.</i>				
Impact of SatisFactory					
	<i>The developed tools offer a user friendly assistance and training to ordinary and extra-ordinary operations in the shop floor in real time.</i>				
	<i>The adoption of the proposed tools and technologies does not require considerable additional workload.</i>				
	<i>The SF framework capitalises the knowledge and experience created on the shop floor and supports a more collaborative and attractive workplace.</i>				

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IMPACT CHECK LIST 2 (DECISION MAKERS)

PILOT SITE:					
#	Criteria	Yes	No	N/A	Remarks
Usability					
	<i>The SF platform provides appropriate visualisation, incident management and decision support components and techniques for the users (e.g. process operators and supervisors).</i>				
	<i>The required information (resources, data and guidelines) is available to the workers in real-time and facilitates timely completion of the necessary tasks.</i>				
	<i>The task of migrating daily activities to be done through the SF platform requires a lot of effort.</i>				
Knowledge Integration					
	<i>The developed platform delivers different views of information depending on the organisational level and localisation of the end-user (i.e. user-specific information).</i>				
	<i>The training platform provides faster and more effective training, helping knowledge and skills enrichment.</i>				
	<i>The relevant shop floor knowledge is managed and analysed through the SF platform.</i>				
Perception of working experience					
	<i>The use of AR tools in daily activities is attractive, time-saving and improves safety on the shop-floor.</i>				
	<i>The SF on-the-job training system is innovative and the visualisations offered facilitate memorisation.</i> <i>The transition from the existing training environment to the SF on-the-job training system using semantic technologies, AR devices and tools leads to faster and more effective training on the shop floor.</i>				

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	<i>The introduced collaboration and gamification elements support team building.</i>				
User Acceptance					
	<i>The introduced SF tools are suitable from the point of view of ergonomics and safety.</i>				
	<i>It is easy to use the SF platform for scheduling, re-adaptation and co-ordination of activities at the shop floor.</i>				
	<i>The introduction of the SF framework is well received and the users are willing to employ the proposed technologies.</i>				
Impact of SatisFactory					
	<i>The use of the SF platform enhances problem solving and decision making capabilities and improves productivity.</i>				
	<i>The SF concepts and tools help balance the workload of employees, ensure safety of workers on the shop floor and reduce work-related stress.</i>				
	<i>The proposed system contributes to the transfiguration of traditional industrial environments into attractive and safe workplaces.</i>				

ANNEX IV: EVALUATION TESTS

EVALUATION TEST ET1: AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET1	Version	1.0
Test Name	Manual assembly operations		
Created by	ATL/REGOLA	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to motivate the interaction between the workers, to increase in the usage and easy access to the knowledge repository of the company, and to timely provide data and instructions to the shop floor. The workers will receive information such as mechanical drawings, connections diagrams, assembly instructions, inspection instructions, packing instructions at the respective working stations through conveniently located HMIs. To this end, the toolkit will be prompted to operate when an assembly operation is required (8 hours per day maximum).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES1.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor/Foreman: He/She is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation. • Workers: They are responsible for the normal operation of the assembly process.
Satisfactory End	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HMI and smart assembly station digital andon: used to

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Users utilized	Tools display the assembly procedure and iterate through steps; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information; • CIDEM: used to store the assembly requiring requests; • Gesture and Recognition Manager: used to interact with the assembly instructions, require assistance, propagate information about the progress status and monitor presence. • Collaboration Platform: used to share knowledge among the workers and problem solving tips • HMI & mobile applications: used to project the notifications and set of information required to perform the task.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not Applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify all the necessary technical information • Retrieve all the necessary technical information from an information system; • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Collaboration among the workers for the successful completion of the task.
Test Procedure	The steps to follow by the tester are the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's SOP for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches; • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the automated support; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the suitability of information provided.
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U2, U7, U11, KI1, KI2, KI12, WE6, WE7, UA8, UA9, OI2, OI3, OI6, OI7, OI8, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Both Production Supervisor and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the equipment. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the emergency level, the location of the malfunction etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

EVALUATION TEST ET2: AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET2	Version	1.0
Test Name	AR Supported assembly operations		
Created by	REGOLA/GLASSUP	Last updated by	
Date created	19/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The main objective of this evaluation test is to reduce the errors and to increase the effectiveness in the manual assembly of a mechanical system. An additional objective is to reduce the stress of the worker and to create a positive feeling to participate into a user community having novel and advanced ways for social interaction and communication.</p> <p>We can distinguish three distinct phases in the evaluation process:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) creation of the “guidance” program, starting from the SOPs and all the necessary basic information. That includes CAD models, descriptions assembly procedures and other multimedia material (eg. 3D animations, audio clips, text messages, 3D models, etc); b) execution, using the virtual and the augmented reality, of the guidance program during the assembly phases; c) collection, during the mounting operating, of all essential Information requested for the subsequent “analytics” phase; the main scope here is to check the goodness of the performed work and make comparisons between different sessions executed in different times.
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES1.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor / Foreman: He / She is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation. • Assembly Procedures Designer: represents the figures dedicated to the task of extracting all the data and

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	<p>information related to the assembly procedures selected in the associated ESs (as well as UCS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content Creation Designer: represents the figure dedicated to the task of enriching the original data (e.g. CAD, description of procedures) producing new content (e.g. animations, videos) • AR Assembly Designer Procedures: represents the figure (only potentially coincident with the precedent) responsible for the collection and derivation of all the data useful for the description of a procedure for AR Tools • CAD designer: the person dedicated to the task of extracting data (as 2D/3D models) involved in the assembly procedures • Worker: is the figure to whom the whole development is mainly addressed. He/she is the person dedicated to the assembly procedures. • Data Analyser: the figure dedicated to analyse the information/data collected in the course of the assembly procedures (e.g. Running times, successes events)
<p>SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR Tools used for the fruition and support the conduct of assembly procedures; • Data Analytics Tools, used for the analysis of information / data collection at runtime; • HMI and smart assembly station digital station: used to display the assembly procedures and iterate through steps; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information; • CIDEM: used to store the assembly operating procedures; • Gesture and Recognition Manager: used to interact with the assembly instructions, require assistance, propagated information about the progress status and presence monitor.
<p>Precondition(s) / Input</p>	<p>Availability of the following items:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) CAD models of the component involved in the procedures 2) description of the assembly procedures 3) environment-related requirements
<p>Postcondition(s) / Output</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retrieve all the necessary technical information from an information system; • Creation of the guidance program; • Visualisation of the necessary technical information; • Provision of actors with the necessary information.

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<p>Test Procedure</p>	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the Following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification and validation of the operational environment preparation; • Installation of all the useful tools on different platforms; • Verification and validation of the provided basic content; • Verification and validation of the derived content; • Verification and validation of the assembly procedures implemented with the augmented reality tool (RA Creation Tool use); • Check the performance "driven" the bonding procedures (AR Visualization Tool use); • Verification of information/data collected at runtime, using tools of Data Analytics; • Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's SOP for a period of time (e.g., two months); • Comparison between the results from Both existing and satisfactory approaches; • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the automated support.
<p>Evaluation Metrics</p>	<p>U1, U2, U3, U11, KI1, KI7, KI11, WE3, WE4, WE6, WE7, UA3, UA7, UA9, OI7, OI9</p>
<p>User Experience Evaluation</p>	<p>The workers will be able to receive support for assembly operations via AR tools. The Supervisor will be able to monitor the status of the progress of the operation.</p>

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EVALUATION TEST ET3: CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET3	Version	1.0
Test Name	Corrective maintenance, re-adaptation and HR workload balancing		
Created by	ATL/ISMB	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to allow the team on the shop floor to respond in case of equipment failure and to resume production in the optimal operating conditions. In this case the complete toolkit to be installed is comprised by the iDSS, re-adaptation, CMMS and HR workload balancing components.</p> <p>The iDSS will be fed with alarms and data analytics from real shop floor data, in order to detect an incident. In case of an equipment failure, the iDSS will suggest actions and interact with the CMMS creating a Work Order, the re-adaptation tool will highlight the occurring malfunction to the supervisor and the HR workload balancing tool will evaluate who is available to respond.</p> <p>To this end, the toolkit will continuously operate when the specific production line is in operating condition (depending on operating hours in each shop floor).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES2.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor/manager: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. • Technicians of Maintenance team (electrical, process, control): They are responsible for the normal operation of the process.

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SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iDSS: used to detect and report the abnormal operation of the process; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; • CIDEM: used to store the alarm events; • HR toolkit & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/ alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Existing of faulty or degraded resistance.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the process; • Identify equipment failure; • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Replacement of faulty equipment with minimum downtime of the operation.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check for identification of the malfunction of the resistance either from the process operator or from the automation (SCADA) system for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches; • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the SatisFactory one; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	U2, U3, U6, U8, U9, U11, KI1, KI2, KI5, KI12, WE1, WE6, WE9, UA2, UA6, UA9, OI1, OI3, OI7, OI8
User Experience Evaluation	Both Process Manager and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the equipment. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the emergency level, the location of the malfunction etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

EVALUATION TEST ET4: PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET4	Version	1.0
Test Name	Preventive maintenance, re-adaptation and HR workload balancing		
Created by	ATL/ISMB	Last updated by	
Date created	18/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to allow the team on the shop floor to organise their preventive maintenance activities in an efficient and more automated way. The complete toolkit to be installed is comprised by the iDSS, re-adaptation, CMMS and HR workload balancing components. The iDSS will be fed with the preventive maintenance schedule from the CMMS and will suggest actions. Considering the workers availability using the HR workload balancing tool it will suggest actions and interact with the CMMS. The re-adaptation tool will allow the Process Manager to review the shop floor status and respond. To this end, the toolkit will continuously operate when the specific production line is in operating condition (depending on the conditions on each shop floor).</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES2.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production supervisor/manager: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. • Technicians of Maintenance team (electrical, process, control): They are responsible for the normal operation of the process.
Satisfactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • iDSS: used to prioritise suggested actions based on predictive maintenance schedules; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute data and SOP;

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CIDEM: used to store SOP and the related information; • HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Existing of faulty or degraded resistance.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the process; • Recognise the need to implement preventive maintenance action; • Readaptation of HR • Timely notification to the involved actors; • Provision of actors with the necessary information to respond; • Depending on trigger, startup or reconfigure the process.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the toolkit; • Concurrent check from the process manager for identification of need for preventive maintenance activities for a period of time (e.g. two months); • Comparison between the results from both existing and SatisFactory approaches (no duplicate preventive maintenance programs, correct rescheduling based on time or units etc.); • Gradually replacement of the existing operation with the SatisFactory one; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U6, U7, U9, U11, KI1, KI12, WE1, WE7, UA1, UA2, U9, UA11, OI3, OI4, OI6, OI8, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	The Process Manager will be able to have a clear view and organise the preventive maintenance schedule and actions required. In case of a need to implement preventive maintenance at a different time due to the experiments or the equipment status, he/she will be notified about the priority level, the required resources etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

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EVALUATION TEST ET5: COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET5	Version	1.0
Test Name	Satisfaction with Suggestions for Improvement Platform		
Created by	FIT	Last updated by	
Date created	11/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation is to assess the satisfaction of shopfloor workers and deciders of the suggestions for improvement platform through user experience evaluation. A frontend where suggestions can be entered, viewed and rated will be installed at the shopfloor. They are being submitted to the respective decider and the feedback (accepted, accepted with modification or rejected with justification) can be requested by the submitter at the frontend again. This is expected to lead to a better knowledge sharing as process knowledge and best practices are distributed within the company.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES5.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decider: He/She has to decide whether a suggestion is accepted (will be put into practice), accepted with modification or rejected with justification. There are different deciders for different suggestion categories • Worker: Submit, view and rate suggestions and request feedback of suggestions submitted by himself
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration Tools: receive, distribute and manage suggestions for improvement; • Middleware: connect different parts of the system; • CIDEM: define data exchange format; • HMI & mobile applications: worker and decider frontends.

Precondition(s) / Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggestions for Improvement • Ratings • Decider feedback
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process ensured • Knowledge shared • User satisfaction achieved
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the backend; • Installation of the network infrastructure; • Installation of the frontends; • Introduction of the system to workers and deciders; • Running the system for 6 months; • User experience assessment of the users
Evaluation Metrics	U1, U2, U3, U5, U6, U7, U10, KI4, KI5, KI8, WE7, WE9, UA2, UA4, UA5, UA8, OI2, OI5
User Experience Evaluation	Standard user experience questionnaires as in Annexe I have to be filled out by the system's end users in order to assess the user experience

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EVALUATION TEST ET6: MONITOR JAR FORMATION OPERATION (DETECTION OF EITHER MANUALLY DRIVEN OR REAL INCIDENTS)

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET6	Version	1.0
Test Name	Monitor Jar Formation Operation (detection of either manually driven or real incidents)		
Created by	CERTH	Last updated by	
Date created	05/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to monitor real jar formation operation under real-life conditions. In this case, infrared cameras monitoring the cells of the batteries are going to be installed. The infrared streaming will be real-time processed, in order to detect potential incident during the process. In case of an accident, an alert event is going to be sent timely at the end-users. To this end, the toolkit will continuously (24 hours per day) monitor the cells' temperature distinguishing the different status (e.g. idle times, start of the process, normal process, incident, etc.) of the operation and send notifications (e.g. alerts) in case of an incident.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES3.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production supervisor: He/She is responsible for the overall production process by monitoring the status of each phase and stage of the production line and assuring its normal operation. Workers: They are responsible for the normal operation of the jar formation process.
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incident detection engine: used to detect and report the abnormal operation of the jar formation process; Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; CIDEM: used to store the alarm events;

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuously monitor the Jar Platforms; Identify any unusual temperature variation above or below the normal; Timely notification to the involved actors.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installation of the infrared (thermal) cameras; Installation of the corresponding toolkit; Concurrent manual check of the cells' temperature for a period of time (e.g. three months); Comparison between the results extracting from both manual (existing one) and automatic approaches; Gradually replacement of the manual operation with the automatic one; Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notification mechanisms.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U4, U8, KI2, WE5, WE6, UA1, UA6, UA12, OI1, OI4, OI5, OI12
User Experience Evaluation	Both Facility Manager and Workers will be able to monitor the status of the Jar formation process. In case of an incident, then they will be notified about the status of the cells, the emergency level, the location of the batteries, etc. through HMIs and the mobile applications of the SatisFactory platform.

EVALUATION TEST ET7: RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET7	Version	1.0
Test Name	Recognition of Incidents with Humans on the Shop-Floor		
Created by	CERTH	Last updated by	
Date created	05/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	1 week		
Iterations	6		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of this evaluation test is to monitor and track the workers in the shop-floor detecting incidents like human falls, collisions, etc. utilizing depth and wearable sensors. In a case of an incident, then the workers will be notified by an alarm message at their HMIs or their mobile devices or even using the central alarm system. Furthermore, the system will be able to detect proactive incidents, which means to predict incidents before they occur. In any case, the alarm message will be accompanied with an emergency level providing information about the status and the type of the incident. Furthermore, optimal roots inside the shop-floors will be provided to the end-users in case of an incident, so as workers avoid extra incidents or dangerous areas in the shop-floor.</p>
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES3.2
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shop-floor related actors: All actors that will work in the shop-floor and more specific at the monitored areas.
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incident detection engine: used to detect and report incidents; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the potential alarm events; • CIDEM: used to store the alarm events; • HMI & mobile applications: used to receive the notifications/

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	alerts.
Precondition(s) / Input	Not applicable.
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously monitor the shop-floor and the workers; • Identify any incidents; • Timely notification to the actors; • Optimal paths in case of proactive and reactive incidents.
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation of the depth and wearable sensors at the shop-floor; • Installation of the corresponding toolkit; • Initiation of the toolkit; • “Simulation” of incidents by actors in the shop-floor very close to the real-conditions; • Evaluation of the usability and the acceptability; • Leave the system for a period of time to test it under real-life shop-floor conditions; • Feedback from the users about the toolkit and the notifications mechanism.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U4, U7, KI2, KI6, WE6, UA1, UA6, UA12, OI1, OI2, OI4, OI5
User Experience Evaluation	<p>All actors in the shop-floor will be notified when an incident occurred or is going to be occurred through their HMIs and their mobile devices. Optimal paths are going to be provided as well. In all cases, actors evaluate the performance of the system, its usability, ease to use features, its visualizations and above all its impact to their everyday working life in the shop-floor.</p>

EVALUATION TEST ET8: ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET8	Version	1.0
Test Name	On-the-job training in assembly operations		
Created by	REGOLA/ATL	Last updated by	
Date created	19/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	<p>The objective of the evaluation test is the reduction in the time and costs of the training. Another objective is the reduction of time and errors occurred in the assembly of systems that are rarely in the year/working time for a workers (less than 10 times per year).</p> <p>We can distinguish two sessions with different objectives:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. create "conditional-based training program" where conditions can however be predetermined in order to easily set the same training conditions to one or more trainee 2. empower communication trainee and trainer
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES4.1, ES4.2, ES4.3
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production Supervisor/Foreman: He/she is responsible for the overall production line or certain parts of it by assuring normal operation • Assembly Procedures Training Designer: represents the figures dedicated to the task of extracting all the data and information related to the training assembly procedures selected in the associated ESs (as well as UCS) • Content Creation Designer: represents the figure dedicated to the task of enriching the original data (e.g. CAD, description of procedures) producing new content (e.g. animations, videos) • AR Assembly Procedures Training Designer: represents the figure (only potentially coincident with the precedent) responsible for the collection and derivation of all the data

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	<p>useful for the description of a procedure for AR Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAD designer: the person dedicated to the task of extracting data (as 2D/3D models) involved in the assembly procedures • Trainer: is the person in charge of training, directly involved during the training sessions (based on the explicit request of Satisfactory to allow two-way communication between trainee / trainer) • Trainee: is the figure to whom the whole training program development is mainly addressed. He/she is the person dedicated to the training assembly procedures. • Data analyser (usually the trainer): the figure dedicated to analyse the information/data collected in the course of the training assembly procedures (e.g. running times, successes events)
<p>Satisfactory End Users Tools utilized</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AR Training Tools used for the fruition and support the conduct of training assembly procedures; • Data Analytics Tools, used for the analysis of information / data collection at runtime; • HMI and smart assembly station digital station: used both to display the assembly procedures and iterate through steps, and to allow the bidirectional communication between trainer and trainee; • Middleware: used to receive and distribute the required information.
<p>Precondition(s) / Input</p>	<p>Availability of the following items:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) CAD models of the component involved in the procedures 2) description of the training assembly procedures 3) environment-related requirements
<p>Postcondition(s) / Output</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformation of SOPs to AR tools; • Provision of actors with the necessary information; • Training of workers; • Collaboration among the workers, the trainers and the trainees for successful completion of the training.
<p>Test Procedure</p>	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification and validation of the operational environment preparation; • Installation of all the useful tools on different platforms; • Verification and validation of the provided basic content • Verification and validation of the derived content; • Verification and validation of the training assembly

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	<p>procedures implemented with the augmented reality tool (AR Creation Tool use);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Check the performance "driven" the bonding procedures (AR Visualization Tool use);• Verification of information / data collected at runtime, using tools of Data Analytics;• Concurrent check for identification and retrieval of information from the company's OP for a period of time (e.g., two months);• Comparison between the results from both existing and satisfactory approaches.
Evaluation Metrics	U3, U11, KI3, KI7, KI9, KI10, KI11, WE2, WE4, WE6, WE8, UA12, OI2, OI5, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Both Production Supervisor and Workers will be able to evaluate the Experience on the basis of the reports automatically created during the execution of the training sessions.

EVALUATION TEST ET9: GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT

Evaluation Test

Test ID	ET9	Version	1.0
Test Name	Gamification Platform		
Created by	FIT	Last updated by	
Date created	11/02/2016	Date last update	
Duration	6 months		
Iterations	2		

Description Scope	The objective of this evaluation is to assess the satisfaction of shopfloor workers of the gamification platform through user experience evaluation. A platform will be installed to which other components can commit points for certain actions. Group points are displayed at a public display and individual points can be requested over a private approach. The aim is motivate workers to perform the actions, especially unpopular actions.
Addressed Evaluation Scenarios	ES5.1
Actor Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • External components: Commit user actions to the gamification platform • Worker: Perform the actual actions • Managers: Grant rewards
SatisFactory End Users Tools utilized	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gamification Platform: receive, provide and manage points, badges, avatars, tasks, players and games; • Middleware: connect different parts of the system; • CIDEM: define data exchange format; • Digital an-don and mobile applications: private and public frontends.
Precondition(s) / Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reported worker actions from external components
Postcondition(s) / Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of performed unpopular tasks increased

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• User satisfaction achieved
Test Procedure	<p>The steps to follow by the tester are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Installation of the backend;• Installation of the network infrastructure;• Installation of the frontends;• Connection to other components;• Collection of number of unpopular tasks for 3 months without the system• Introduction of the system to workers and deciders;• Running the system for 3 months;• Collection of number of unpopular tasks with the system• User experience assessment of the users
Evaluation Metrics	U10, KI4, WE9, UA1, UA8, UA10, UA11, OI2, OI4, OI5, OI7, OI9
User Experience Evaluation	Standard user experience questionnaires as in Annexe I have to be filled out by the system's end users in order to assess the user experience

ANNEX V: RESULTS AT CERTH/CPERI

EVALUATION SCENARIO 1

Results from Workers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	50.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	25.00%	50.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%

Results for ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	25.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%
Agree	75.00%	33.33%	33.33%	50.00%	100.00%	33.33%	66.67%	100.00%	75.00%	33.33%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	50.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	66.67%

Results for ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%
Agree	66.67%	33.33%	33.33%	66.67%	100.00%	33.33%	66.67%	100.00%	100.00%	33.33%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	50.00%	25.00%	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	25.00%	62.50%	12.50%	62.50%	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	25.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	12.50%	12.50%	25.00%	0.00%
Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	37.50%
Strongly Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	62.50%

Results for ET1.1 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	25.00%	50.00%	62.50%	12.50%	37.50%	12.50%	25.00%	0.00%	75.00%	37.50%
Agree	50.00%	37.50%	12.50%	0.00%	50.00%	87.50%	75.00%	0.00%	12.50%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	25.00%	12.50%	12.50%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	12.50%	12.50%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	14.29%	42.86%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	42.86%	57.14%	0.00%	71.43%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	14.29%	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%
Disagree	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	57.14%
Strongly Disagree	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	42.86%

Results for ET2.1 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	71.43%	42.86%	0.00%	28.57%	71.43%	42.86%	33.33%	28.57%	0.00%	57.14%
Agree	28.57%	42.86%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	57.14%	50.00%	57.14%	42.86%	28.57%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	14.29%	14.29%	0.00%	16.67%	14.29%	28.57%	14.29%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%

Results from Decision Makers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Disagree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%

Results for ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for decision makers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	66.67%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	33.33%	0.00%
Disagree	66.67%	0.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	100.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET1.2 AUTOMATED SUPPORT FOR ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	25.00%	25.00%	25.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Agree	25.00%	50.00%	75.00%	25.00%	25.00%	100.00%	25.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Disagree	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%
Disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET2.2 AR SUPPORTED ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

EVALUATION SCENARIO 2

Results from Workers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	40.00%	40.00%	40.00%	40.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	80.00%	20.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	40.00%	20.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Disagree	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	60.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%

Results for ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Agree	60.00%	60.00%	20.00%	60.00%	20.00%	80.00%	60.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	60.00%	100.00%
Disagree	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Question

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	60.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Agree	40.00%	20.00%	60.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	40.00%	40.00%	80.00%	20.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Disagree	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%

Results for ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	80.00%	80.00%	40.00%	20.00%	40.00%	40.00%	40.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	80.00%	60.00%	60.00%	20.00%	60.00%	0.00%	60.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	33.33%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	50.00%	16.67%
Neither agree nor disagree	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	33.33%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	33.33%
Strongly Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	66.67%	0.00%	33.33%	0.00%	50.00%

Results for ET3.1 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	45.45%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Agree	36.36%	60.00%	20.00%	60.00%	20.00%	80.00%	60.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	9.09%	20.00%	40.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	60.00%	100.00%
Disagree	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	9.09%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	14.29%	42.86%	71.43%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	85.71%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	14.29%	28.57%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	14.29%	14.29%	42.86%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	14.29%	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	28.57%	0.00%	0.00%	42.86%	0.00%	28.57%	0.00%	14.29%	0.00%	14.29%
Strongly Disagree	42.86%	0.00%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	71.43%	0.00%	57.14%	0.00%	85.71%

Results for ET4.1 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING –Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	50.00%	16.67%	50.00%	25.00%	33.33%	25.00%	16.67%	8.33%	25.00%	25.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	33.33%	41.67%	33.33%	41.67%	41.67%	8.33%	66.67%	16.67%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	33.33%	16.67%	33.33%	33.33%	33.33%	16.67%	25.00%	0.00%	33.33%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	16.67%	16.67%	8.33%	25.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	41.67%	0.00%	0.00%

Results from Decision Makers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING –Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%

Results for ET3.2 CORRECTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Disagree	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET4.2 PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE, RE-ADAPTATION & HR WORKLOAD BALANCING –Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

EVALUATION SCENARIO 3

Results from Workers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET6.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

Results for ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	40.00%	20.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	80.00%	20.00%	20.00%	60.00%	80.00%	20.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Disagree	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	60.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR –Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	20.00%	80.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	60.00%	40.00%	20.00%	40.00%	80.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	80.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	80.00%	60.00%	20.00%
Disagree	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET6.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	40.00%	100.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	80.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Agree	20.00%	60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Strongly Disagree	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	60.00%

Results for ET6.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	20.00%	60.00%	40.00%	60.00%	60.00%	80.00%	80.00%	20.00%	80.00%	80.00%
Agree	80.00%	40.00%	20.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Agree	20.00%	60.00%	60.00%	0.00%	80.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	80.00%	0.00%	80.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	40.00%
Strongly Disagree	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	60.00%

Results for ET7.1 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	20.00%	60.00%	40.00%	40.00%	60.00%	40.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	40.00%
Agree	60.00%	40.00%	40.00%	60.00%	40.00%	60.00%	20.00%	40.00%	40.00%	60.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results from Decision Makers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET6.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

Results for ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	100.00%	50.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET6.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET6.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS IN EQUIPMENT/OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET7.2 RECOGNITION OF INCIDENTS WITH HUMANS ON THE SHOP-FLOOR – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Agree	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

EVALUATION SCENARIO 4

Results from Workers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Question

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	37.50%	25.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	75.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	75.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	25.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	62.50%	0.00%	25.00%
Strongly Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	37.50%	0.00%	75.00%

Results for ET8.1 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	25.00%	12.50%	25.00%	37.50%	25.00%	50.00%	37.50%	50.00%	37.50%	37.50%
Agree	75.00%	62.50%	50.00%	37.50%	50.00%	12.50%	25.00%	37.50%	50.00%	25.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	12.50%	25.00%	25.00%	25.00%	25.00%	37.50%	12.50%	12.50%	37.50%
Disagree	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	12.50%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results from Decision Makers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%
Disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%

Results for ET8.2 ON-THE-JOB TRAINING IN ASSEMBLY OPERATIONS – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Agree	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%

EVALUATION SCENARIO 5

Results from Workers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

Results for ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT– General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	20.00%	80.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	80.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	80.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	40.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	60.00%
Strongly Disagree	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	40.00%

Results for ET5.1 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	40.00%	60.00%	40.00%	20.00%
Agree	60.00%	40.00%	100.00%	60.00%	60.00%	60.00%	40.00%	20.00%	40.00%	40.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	40.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%

Results for ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	80.00%	80.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	80.00%	20.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%	0.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%
Strongly Disagree	60.00%	0.00%	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	60.00%

Results for ET9.1 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	KI2 Knowledge Integration	KI1 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	OI2 Overall Impact	OI3 Overall Impact	OI7 Overall Impact	OI9 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	40.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	20.00%
Agree	60.00%	40.00%	60.00%	60.00%	40.00%	40.00%	60.00%	40.00%	40.00%	60.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	40.00%	0.00%	20.00%	40.00%	60.00%	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	20.00%
Disagree	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	20.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results from Decision Makers' Questionnaires

1st Data Collection

Results for ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General and Specific Question

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

Results for ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General and Specific Questions

The degree of development of the associated tools, together with the progress of the implementations at the CERTH/CPERI pilot were not mature enough for workers to proceed with the evaluation in the 1st Data Collection.

2nd Data Collection

Results for ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	50.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Disagree	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET5.2 COLLABORATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Agree	50.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – General Questions

	I found the system unnecessarily complex	I think that I would like to use this system frequently	I thought the system was easy to use	I think that I would need the support of an experienced person to be able to use this system	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	I would imagine that most application developers would learn to use this system very quickly	I found the system very cumbersome to use	I felt very confident using the system	I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Agree	0.00%	100.00%	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Disagree	100.00%	0.00%	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	100.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%

Results for ET9.2 GAMIFICATION IN SHOP FLOOR WORKING ENVIRONMENT – Specific Questions

KPI Criterion	U2 Usability	U11 Usability	K12 Knowledge Integration	K11 Knowledge Integration	WE7 Working Experience	UA9 User Acceptance	O12 Overall Impact	O13 Overall Impact	O17 Overall Impact	O19 Overall Impact
Strongly Agree	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%	50.00%
Agree	50.00%	100.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	50.00%
Neither agree nor disagree	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	50.00%	0.00%	0.00%	50.00%	0.00%
Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Strongly Disagree	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%